

OPEN SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION IN THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA FOR SSH - PREPARATION

WP7 Communication, Outreach and Advocacy

D 7.4 Report of activities on communication, outreach and networking

June 30, 2021

Deliverable 7.4

Report of activities on communication outreach and networking

Grant Agreement number	: 871069
Project acronym	: OPERAS-P
Project title	: Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for SSH - Preparation
Funding Scheme	: INFRADEV-02-2019-2020
Project's coordinator Organization	: CNRS-OpenEdition
E-mail address	: pierre.mounier@openedition.org
Website	: https://www.operas.unito.it/projects/operas-p/
WP and tasks contributing	: WP7, T7.1, T7.2, T7.3 and T7.4
WP leader	: Max Weber Stiftung (MWS)
Dissemination level	: public
Due date	: June 30, 2021
Delivery date	: June 30, 2021
Authors	: Judith Schulte, Kelly Achenbach, Marina Angelaki, Lorena Caliman, Elisabeth Ernst, Mateusz Franczak, Elena Giglia, Iraklis Katsaloulis, Tom Mosterd, Magdalena Wnuk
Contributors	: Claire Clivaz, Christina Cantrel, Suzanne Dumouchel, Chloé Lebon, Pierre Mounier, Stefanie Pohle, Valérié Schafer

Contents

Abstract	4
General Introduction/Consideration	4
General Introduction into the WP	4
Communication on the project (Task 7.1)	5
General Aspects of the OPERAS-P communication strategy	5
Main Aim and Target Audiences	5
Building community and researching user needs	6
Alignment of the communication of the project with the infrastructure	7
Presentations, conferences and workshops	7
OPERAS Events: Workshops and Conferences	7
Presentations at external conferences, workshops etc.	18
Communication activities of partner institutions etc., Press Release	20
Website operas-eu.org	24
OPERAS Blog	26
Social Media Activities	31
Newsletter	36
Dissemination	39
Publications	40
Videos	42
Main Impact, Increase of communication activities	43
General Considerations	43
Open Science and dissemination	43
How the pandemic affected the work in the WP	44
Future plans and considerations	44
Outreach for new members (Task 7.2)	45
Definition of Outreach	45
Activities and Results	45
Future Strategy	49
Conclusion	49
Networking (Task 7.3)	50
Definition of Networking	50
Activities and results	50
Alliances	51
OPERAS in the arena	51
Creating a community, starting with Early Career Researchers	52
Further initiatives	52
Advocacy towards researchers (Task 7.4)	53

Definition of Advocacy	53
Advocacy Workshops and results	54
Appendix:	57
Examples of communication activities of partners in detail:	57

1) Abstract

This report describes the results of WP7 Communication, Outreach and Advocacy of the OPERAS-P project. It describes the communication activities, communication channels and the outreach and networking results of the work done within the OPERAS-P project in collaboration with the communication on the OPERAS research infrastructure (RI).

2) General Introduction/Consideration

a) General Introduction into the WP

The objective of work package 7 was to communicate on OPERAS-P objectives, services and products to related stakeholders and to advocate, network and build synergies to increase the uptake of OPERAS-P goals. The activities were aligned with T2.1, the vision and theory of OPERAS, that was further developed within the time of the project.

In particular the focus was placed on:

- developing a communication and dissemination strategy;
- raising awareness and stimulating interest in OPERAS-P work through the use of various communication channels (Task 7.1);
- reaching out to new potential members of the OPERAS infrastructure (Task 7.2);
- networking to create strategic alliances and addressing the cultural challenge of Open Science in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) (Task 7.3)
- organising a number of activities to advocate Open Science in the SSH towards scholars, particularly early career researchers

This report describes in detail the results of the work done within this work package. It describes the events done, analyses the metrics of the communication channels and gives links to publications and reports. Then it shows the results of the outreach work done within the project and the networks that have been built up.

3) Communication on the project (Task 7.1)

a) General Aspects of the OPERAS-P communication strategy

i) Main Aim and Target Audiences

The OPERAS-P external communication strategy aimed to:

1. communicate the OPERAS-P project results and the acknowledgement of its EU-funding to a large audience of stakeholders and target groups.
2. promote the OPERAS research infrastructure (RI), including its services, its mission and vision in the field of scholarly communication in SSH, its services and community.

The goals of OPERAS' communication strategy were, first, to advocate for open scholarly communication in SSH and then to encourage potential interested parties to join OPERAS. Therefore, relaying the nature of OPERAS as an inclusive, community-driven infrastructure was a key component of its communication strategy.

The overall aim of the communication measures were to maintain a high public awareness of the OPERAS RI and a positive public image. The aim was to reach a corporate reputation of the infrastructure in regards to trust, respect, reliability and credibility.

OPERAS communication aims were to present OPERAS as a distributed infrastructure that relies on active members in many countries, with services for SSH researchers, with a strong community (research institutions, libraries, platforms, publishers, funders ...), in active exchange with the other ERICS, open for new partners, with an open governance structure (community-driven and scholar-led) and open activities. The aims were adapted with the further development of the RI and the work done within the project. So within the project time the need for the further description of the RI as community-driven and scholar-led came stronger into focus as well as the possibilities of relying on strong members as national nodes that were better able to reach the national communities for communication.

Another aim was to spread the results of the OPERAS-P project like to address users of the OPERAS-PKP Forum, the OPERAS catalogue of service (especially the connection to the EOSC), the work done in WP6 on the innovation of scholarly writing and to reach the different stakeholder groups with this results.

According to the latest analysis of stakeholders (prepared by the university of Zadar for the Landscape Study T2.3), OPERAS targets eight stakeholder groups. The most important group is SSH researchers as they are the main users of the services.

The eight target groups are defined as follows:

1. SSH Researchers (under different roles: Information Seekers, Readers, Authors, Reviewers, Editors)
2. Scholarly Communication service providers

- a. Publishers (University presses, publishing departments in academic institutions, publishers, scholar-led publishers, scholarly societies, commercial publishers (SMEs, Bigs))
- b. Dissemination platforms and repositories (institutional, national, international)
- c. Other digital tools and services providers (authoring tools and services providers, peer-reviewing tools and services providers, copy-editing tools and services providers, annotation tools and services providers, marketplace tools and services, library tools and services)
3. Research policy makers (ministries of research and higher education, research councils, evaluation agencies)
4. Funders (regional funding agencies, national funding agencies, charities and private funders, international funders)
5. Institutions (universities and RPOs), (central administrations, academic libraries, research departments)
6. Infrastructures (E-infrastructures and research infrastructures: international, European, national, regional)
7. Society/Socio-economic actors (journalists, associations, administrations, SMEs, “movements”, creative class, amateurs)
8. OPERAS members, OPERAS-P, TRIPLE and COESO consortia and CO-OPERAS network

ii) Building community and researching user needs

One main aim of the OPERAS communication is to include all members into the communication activities. As the infrastructure is distributed across several European countries, the most effective way to disseminate the OPERAS brand and results is by activating the OPERAS members to present OPERAS. The activities of the members to present OPERAS to their communities and networks were actively included into the OPERAS communication strategy, as this seems to be the most efficient way to reach out to broader communities. Therefore, especially the core members were included in promoting events, activities, joint policies and surveys to get in contact with the potential users.

One example in 2020 was the survey prepared by the University of Zadar, addressed to all SSH researchers, to understand their scholarly communication practices and define their needs. It was translated into 8 languages and sent through our communication channels, including mailing lists, communication officers at universities, and the core members were asked to spread it within their countries.

OPERAS / OPERAS-P / PARTNERS / UNIVERSITY OF ZADAR
07/04/2020

Help us find out more about scholarly communication practices

OPERAS runs a survey directed at researchers to find out more about current practices, habits and issues relating to social sciences and humanities (SSH) scholarly communication. The OPERAS-P project builds and co-ordinates services, practices...

Dear researchers from social sciences and **#humanities**, we need your help! We need 300 answers per country. Still a long way to go ...

Please take 10 minutes for our survey available in 8 languages: operas-eu.org/3932

#Europa @EASSH_ #SSH #HSS
#scholcomm #Openaccess
pic.twitter.com/EEEx129KfJG

Blog post and tweet on the survey.

iii) Alignment of the communication of the project with the infrastructure

The OPERAS-P project and its logo aimed to strengthen the branding of the OPERAS infrastructure in order to support it to become a European RI. Therefore, OPERAS-P's visual identity is based on the visual identity of the OPERAS RI that had been established in the previous OPERAS-D project. This ensures continuity in terms of visual identity throughout OPERAS' different stages of development.

b) Presentations, conferences and workshops

Events are a very efficient method to reach different audiences with communication measures and present results. All events and presentations were

i) OPERAS Events: Workshops and Conferences

To include the audience and to make sure OPERAS is a community-built RI, several events were organised within the OPERAS-P project. Additionally, it was important to address the community and the different stakeholder groups. Presentations on conferences and workshops can be seen as part of the communication of the project and the general brand as well as building networks with potential partners, but can be seen as part of the dissemination of results as well.

In the first section below all OPERAS initiated and organised events are listed. The second section includes all events where a member from the consortium who introduced OPERAS and/or OPERAS-P results was present.

Not directly listed here are all partners' internal events, where OPERAS and OPERAS-P results were presented within the partners institutions, or general events that are related to OPERAS, such as the "Tuesday on open science" webinars of the University of Zadar.

Type of event	Number of events	Stakeholder groups reached (as defined above)	Number of attendees	OPERAS-P results presented	Additional 1. communication and 2. dissemination measures
Conferences	2	all defined stakeholder groups 1-8	532	D2.3, WP6, D6.2	1. Tweets, own website, mailing lists, newsletter, personal invitations, videos, 2. presentations published
Regional Events	5	all defined stakeholder groups 1-8	433	T3.3, T 2.3, D4.1, D4.4, D6.2	1. Tweets, blog posts, mailing lists/newsletters, personal invitations, 2. reports
Workshops	5	different stakeholders within the different topics: 1,2, 5, 6, 7, 8	515	results WP 6 complete, T 2.3, D4.1, D4.4, D6.2	1. Tweets, blog posts, reports, one workshop was placed at Munin Conference, 2. reports, video, presentations

1. Conferences:

OPERAS
CONFERENCE

Opening up Social Sciences and Humanities in Europe: From Promises to Reality

OPERAS-P
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 871869

Max Weber Stiftung
Deutsche Geisteswissenschaftliche Institute im Ausland

www.operas-eu.org

Title: “**Opening up Social Sciences and Humanities in Europe: From Promises to Reality**” (OPERAS annual conference)

Date: 2–4 November 2020

N of attendants: 486

Stakeholders: OPERAS community, politicians, funders, librarians, infrastructure providers, researchers

Topics: Current development in Open Science, advocating for scholarly communication, addressing Open Science in Europe, defining OPERAS services

Documentation/Reports: conference page: www.operas2020.com, videos:

<https://perspectivia.net/publikationen/operas2020>, <https://doi.org/10.25360/01-2021-00011>,

<https://doi.org/10.25360/01-2021-00012>, <https://doi.org/10.25360/01-2021-00013>,

<https://doi.org/10.25360/01-2021-00014>;

website: <https://www.operas-eu.org/operas2020-conference/>

details on the program can be found here and links to presentations

3 days, 1 keynote, 5 panels, 4 workshops, 3 virtual lounges, 38 presenters, 63 experts, 486 participants, 1100 minutes

The OPERAS annual conference in 2020, “Opening up Social Sciences and Humanities in Europe: From Promises to Reality,” was held online via Zoom on 2–4 November.

Participants took part in a combination of panels/panel discussions, workshops, presentations and virtual networking opportunities as described below:

Day 1 (2 November 2020): Discussing current development for Open Science and advocating scholarly communication

Title: How to advocate for social sciences and humanities

Date: November 2, 2020

N of attendants: 80+

Stakeholders: institutions, researchers, research infrastructures, NGOs

Topics: advocacy, scholarly communication, public communication of science, research evaluation, research policies, funders, interdisciplinary collaboration, policy makers

Documentation/Reports: <https://www.operas2020.com/>

Summary:

Moderator: Sally Chambers, Ghent Centre for Digital Humanities

Chairs: Elisabeth Ernst, Mateusz Franczak

Panelists: Marc Vanholsbeeck, Alíz Horváth, Jane Ohlmeyer, Jack Spaapen, Nina Kancewicz-Hoffman

The Advocacy SIG envisions to develop a strategy on how to advocate for the SSH disciplines, particularly targeting funders and policy-makers, both at national and at European levels.

The goal of this panel was to develop a strategy on how to advocate for the SSH disciplines and to target funders and policy makers, both at national and at European levels.

Conclusions were based on the professional experience of the panelists. Information obtained from the presentations and discussion during the conference was meant to supply the documentation for OPERAS to present to community and policy makers. Best practices featured in case studies could be later shared with new members as a basis to operate on EU and national levels. Exchanging experiences connected to advocacy, showing examples of best practices and challenges or obstacles related to local specifics during the panel provided input for the Advocacy SIG work, but was also intended to attract new organizations to join OPERAS and become active within the community.

During the panel Jane Ohlmeyer presented SHAPE-ID's work on delivering a set of recommendations, to guide policymakers, funders, research performing institutions and researchers in achieving successful pathways to interdisciplinary integration. (slides: 10.5281/zenodo.5017522)

Jack Spaapen spoke about the importance of collaboration among different disciplines, business and industry, civil society and government at all levels, as well as how we strengthen the role and position of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences in EU and beyond.

Alíz Horváth explained how the Humanista podcast promotes humanities globally to reach broader audiences and how podcasts can help listeners understand complex social issues, such as migration, development or belonging based on the Social Sciences and Humanities (AH). (slides: 10.5281/zenodo.5017503)

Nina Kancewicz-Hoffman presented the activities of the Standing Committee for Social Sciences (SCSS) of the European Science Foundation (ESF), which supported diverse research and strategic activities in research policy domain. We learned how crucial it is to have good partners in academia and on the policy side and that promoting social sciences results for policy making requires a long-term approach.

Marc Vanholsbeeck spoke about the opportunities and challenges that the pandemic has brought to light for Open Science in general, and more specifically for the fostering of the openness paradigm within the Social Sciences and Humanities. (slides: 10.5281/zenodo.5017546)

A Plan S for Academic Books: Voices from the Community (panel), 09:30-12:00

The workshop was composed of a panel discussion with OA book experts followed by a collective writing session to produce a report that formed the basis of feedback to cOAlition S to support them in their policy development for OA books.

Chairs/Moderators: Jon Deer (EASSH), Pierre Mounier (OPERAS), Vanessa Proudman (SPARC Europe), Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra (DARIAH)

Speakers: Prof. Martin Paul Eve, Agata Morka, Lara Speicher, Victoria Tsoukala, Koen Vermeir

EOSC Co-Creation: Anticipating the future of research in the social sciences and humanities (workshop), 14:00-16:00

Co-organised by OPERAS, the EOSC Secretariat, and KBR, this workshop inquired not only about social sciences and humanities (SSH) researchers' actual needs with respect to research infrastructures, services and policies, but also about their visions and future needs.

The workshop first introduced the European research landscape in the SSH, through presentations of OPERAS, the EOSC Secretary and the SSHOC project. Practical implementations were then described: The Cultural heritage charter and KBR services related to TDM and SSH data management. The attendees were then invited to contribute to the discussion in four breakout sessions.

Chairs/Moderators: Sally Chambers, Laure Barbot, Andreas Rauber, Arnaud Gingold, Francesca Di Donato

Speakers: Julie Birkholz, Sally Chambers, Laure Barbot, Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra, Andreas Rauber, Arnaud Gingold

Open Access Journals and Plan S: Ready to Go? (panel), 14:00-16:00

In this workshop the implications of Plan S for Open Access journals in the social sciences and humanities were discussed, giving voice to experts on scientific, technical, political and organisational issues. To set the framework, the overview of the existing infrastructure and preliminary results of the Diamond Open Access journals were presented. Then possible strategies, funding schemes, risks, business models, and operational choices were discussed.

Chairs/Moderators: Elena Giglia, Jadranka Stojanovski

Speaker: Bianca Kramer, Jeroen Bosman, Dominic Mitchell, Saskia de Vries, Johan Rooryck, Vanessa Proudman

Day 2 (3 November 2020): Addressing Open Science in Europe

Opening and Keynote: Scientific communities and infrastructures: a personal perspective (presentation and discussion), 9:30-10:45

Johan Rooryck presented his personal experience as an editor of the subscription journal *Lingua*, whose community moved to the Open Access journal *Glossa* in 2015. Open Access initially was a way to take back control of the journal's governance. The transition process also made him realize the essential role of the journal as a community rather than as a tool for communication or a title in a publisher's list (e.g. [Montgomery & Neylon 2019](#)). This in turn led him to consider issues of governance, control, and organization of the scholarly community and the infrastructure needed for this purpose.

Keynote Speaker: Johan Rooryck

Chairs/Moderators: Jadranka Stojanovski, Suzanne Dumouchel, Judith Schulte

OPERAS Research Infrastructure in 90': mission, vision, action (panel), 11:00-12:30

In this panel, Jadranka Stojanovski introduced the scholarly communication landscape in Europe for social sciences and humanities. She presented the results of a survey done in the OPERAS-P project: What are the current practices, habits and issues in scholarly communication? Afterwards, Delfim Leão presented the survey results on "Multilingualism in Social Sciences and Humanities," which he and his team at Coimbra University conducted in OPERAS-P to prepare a future platform aimed at supporting translation of SSH content. Next, Maciej Maryl presented the "Future of Scholarly Writing in Social Sciences and Humanities" paper prepared by IBL-PAN in the context of OPERAS-P project, which stands as the scientific case for the OPERAS infrastructure. As the last presentation Yoann Moranville (Technical Coordinator of OPERAS) and Pierre Mounier (Coordinator of OPERAS) gave an overview on the current developments and future plans of the OPERAS services: Certification Service, Discovery Service, Metrics Service, Publishing Service Portal, Research for Society Service and Future Services. In this presentation, the common governance scheme of OPERAS services was also presented.

Speakers: Jadranka Stojanovski, Delfim Leão, Maciej Maryl, Yoann Moranville, Pierre Mounier

How social sciences and humanities infrastructures should address Open Science challenges in Europe (panel), 14:00-16:00

The topic in this panel was how Open Science principles are implemented in different social sciences and humanities research infrastructures and, more largely, how they change social sciences and humanities research. The different panelists from the European Commission and research infrastructures such as DARIAH ERIC, CLARIN ERIC addressed the question: How can we shape the future based on the Open Science principles and the constraints faced by social sciences and humanities? They discussed issues related to open publications, evaluation of research, data management, interdisciplinarity and missing competences. (Kosta Glinos' slides: 10.5281/zenodo.5017403)

Chairs/Moderators: Lino Paula, Suzanne Dumouchel

Speaker: Kostas Glinos, Jennifer Edmond, Ron Dekker, Olivier Bouin, Franciska de Jong

Day 3 (4 November 2020): OPERAS community at work: Defining OPERAS services

Title: *An Open Infrastructure for the Open Access Book: Needs & Challenges from a Library Perspective*

Date: November 4, 2020

Number of attendants: 50+

Stakeholders: Librarians

Topics: Open infrastructure & open access books, needs, challenges, introduction DOAB, introduction OAPEN, OA book number (usage, number of OA books, publishers engaging countries, etc.), OA Books Toolkit, SCOSS, infrastructure funding & sustainability, four library perspectives: U.S.; Swedish; Danish & Belgium. OA-fund, green OA, diamond OA, gold OA.

Documentation / reports: https://perspectivia.net/receive/pnet_mods_00004267#

Summary

As part of the OPERAS 2020 Conference the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB) held its annual Stakeholder Committee meeting in the form of an online workshop for its members, and was open to the wider scholarly community. In line with the theme of the conference: "Opening up Social Sciences and Humanities in Europe: From Promises to Reality" the workshop zoomed in on open infrastructure for open access books and, more specifically, looking at the needs and challenges from a library perspective.

The session was moderated by Neil Jacobs (UKRI & Chair DOAB Supervisory Board) and, following a brief introduction on DOAB and OAPEN, our four library panellists shared initial statements, kicking-off what turned out to be a fruitful discussion and workshop.

DOAB and OAPEN - Two infrastructures enabling open access for books

At the start of this workshop, Eelco Ferwerda (DOAB & OAPEN) offered a concise introduction to DOAB and OAPEN and how these two platforms promote and work with open access books. While they are two independent platforms, each catering to different needs

around open access books, there are certain synergies where both platforms connect to offer better discoverability of open access books. With the OAPEN Library hosting full-text books and offering services in areas, such as usage reporting and preservation, it offers distinct services compared to DOAB, which in turn offers a central and trusted resource linking to OA book titles and providing reliable information on OA publishers.

Four perspectives from the Library community

With a better view of the infrastructure presently available for open access books, we turned to four library panellists who shared a brief statement on the particular challenges and needs from their perspective:

Jeff Edmunds (Penn State University Libraries) elaborated on a number of challenges such as there being no or poor metadata quality for open access books; duplication, where the same titles available from multiple platforms are not easily handled by traditional systems; and passive resistance from colleagues when it comes to actively supporting open access for books and its infrastructure. From here we continued with a Danish perspective by Joanna Ball (Roskilde University Library & Danish Royal Library). The Danish focus has very much been on green open access and neither the national nor the research councils' open access policy includes monographs.

“In Denmark, centralised efforts are starting to prioritise the supporting of infrastructure and services necessary for Open Access, though these funds do not directly come from library budgets.”

Moving to Sweden, Sofie Wennström (Stockholm University Library) mentions a different approach where the government's goal is to have all centrally funded scholarly publications Open Access by 2026. While the main emphasis has been on journal articles, Stockholm University Press and the Kriterium infrastructure offer open access book publishing options. Still libraries seem to struggle with reaching out to researchers who remain hesitant to change their way of doing things even if they support the general idea of open access.

A fourth perspective coming from Belgium, is presented by Demmy Verbeke (KU Leuven Libraries), who initiated the KU Leuven Fund for Fair Open Access in 2018: a fund consciously set up not to generally support open access but to particularly support non-profit and community-owned initiatives. It is used to subsidize OA monograph publishing by KU Leuven University Press and innovative publishing initiatives and infrastructure.

“This [application of the KU Leuven Fund] is thus not unlike the approach advocated by David Lewis to set aside at least 2,5% of the total library budget to support common infrastructure needed to create the open scholarly commons.”

TRIPLE Discovery artefacts workshop (workshop), 10:00-11:30
Chairs/Moderators: Stefano De Paoli, Paula Forbes, Olena Saienko

Trust building systems: Who is in the room? (workshop), 10:00-11:30
Chairs/Moderators: Maxime Bouillard, Gaël Van Weyenbergh

How to join OPERAS (presentation), 10:00-11:30

This meeting virtually gathered organisations interested in joining OPERAS RI and provided them with the opportunity to discuss with core partners of OPERAS how they see their role in the research infrastructure and to show possibilities to work together within the research infrastructure community.

At the meeting, different types of memberships were presented, as well as the OPERAS Special Interest Groups. In addition, OPERAS members talked about their experiences as partners. A Q & A session allowed an interactive discussion among all participants.

Chairs/Moderators: Marina Angelaki, Iraklis Katsaloulis

OPERAS Assembly of the commons, 14:00-16:30

The Assembly of the Commons was a closed meeting for OPERAS members where they could engage within its diversity and for the Special Interest Groups to work together on different topics: Advocacy, Best Practices, Common Standards, Multilingualism, Open Access Business Models, Tools Research and Development.

The graphic features a large, stylized 'P' shape in shades of purple and red. Inside the 'P' is a laptop icon with a video call interface showing three participants. To the right of the 'P' is a network diagram with nodes and connecting lines. Text elements include the OPERAS-P logo, the event title 'Final Meeting', the date and time 'June 29 11.30-13.00', the location 'CEST, virtually', and the project description 'OPERAS-P Project: Building up OPERAS as a community-driven infrastructure'. Logos for the University of Turin and the OPERAS-P project are also present, along with a small European Union funding notice.

OPERAS·P
Final Meeting

June 29
11.30–13.00
CEST, *virtually*

OPERAS-P Project:
Building up
OPERAS as a
community-driven
infrastructure

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
DI TORINO

www.operas-eu.org **OPERAS·P**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 871069

Title: OPERAS-P Project: building up OPERAS as a community-driven infrastructure
OPERAS-P final meeting

Date: 29 June 2021

Online

N of attendants: 46

Stakeholders: OPERAS-P Consortium and OPERAS members, Librarians, Researcher

Topics: Overview of OPERAS-P results useful for the community, further ways to be involved in OPERAS

Documentation/Reports: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5040976>

2. Regional Events/National Node Events

Title: Name: "Workshop - Supporting open communication in SHS on a French and European scale: the OPERAS infrastructure"

Date: 28 June 2021

Online

N of attendants: 82, 145 registered

Stakeholders: Researchers, Publishers, Infrastructure providers

Topics: Presentation of OPERAS, Focus on the SIG Tools, the Pathfinder, 3 projects (TRIPLE, COESO & CO-OPERAS) and the French strategy

Documentation: <https://leo.hypotheses.org/17647>

Title: Building Research Infrastructures and Communities for Open Scholarly Communications in the Humanities and Social Sciences

Date: 22 June 2021

Online

N of attendants: 33 (47 registered)

Stakeholders: Researchers, Librarians, University Presses, Funders, Research Infrastructures (CLARIAH, SURF, DANS etc.)

Topics: The OPERAS Research Infrastructure, what it is, what it is not. Why OPERAS is important to the Netherlands. Experiences with OPERAS in France, and reflections on the relations to the Netherlands. Involvement and next steps for OPERAS.

Documentation/Reports: Programme link: <https://tinyurl.com/jcsu7sve>.

Title: Polish National Node Meeting (OPERAS-PL – komunikacja w humanistyce i naukach społecznych)

Date: 17 June 2021

Online

N of attendants: 67 (116 registered, 97 subscribed for OPERAS-PL newsletter)

Stakeholders: Researchers, Academic Teachers, Librarians, Publishers, Editors

Topics: what is OPERAS, goals and actions of the OPERAS-PL, open access in Poland in the light of the OPERAS survey on scholarly communication, needs of the Polish SSH community regarding OA publishing and scholarly communication.

Documentation/ Reports:

[link to the post on OPERAS blog on Monday 28th]

[Event Facebook page](#)

Title: Building communities for the promotion of Open Scholarly Communication in Social Sciences and Humanities (OPERAS Greek Node Workshop)

Date: 26 May 2021

Online

N of attendants: 168 (490 registered)

Stakeholders: Researchers, Librarians, Publishers, Phd Students, Post- Graduate Students , Funders

Topics: Policies for Open Science in the EU, what is OPERAS and how it works, members of the Greek SSH community talked about their experiences from the adoption of open practices, presentation of OPERAS services, presentation of networking activities

Documentation/Reports: <https://www.ekt.gr/en/events/program/25796>;

<https://www.ekt.gr/en/events/25795>; <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tajU01971EU&t=54s>

Title: OPERAS per la comunità italiana - OPERAS for the Italian community (OPERAS Italian Node workshop)

Date: 13 May 2021

N. of attendants: 33/59 registered

Stakeholders: researchers, librarians, publishers

Topics: after an overview of what OPERAS is, what has been done and what is planning for the future, researchers were invited to have their say on the expectations for a national node of a research infrastructure.

Report: The presentation and the recording (in Italian) are available on Zenodo,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4761082> .

After the event, a mailing list was created, to keep in touch with the participants:

operas-nodo-italiano@googlegroups.com

Title: **Networking the Networks – Opening OPERAS-GER** (German National Node Workshop)

Date: 26 April 2021

Online

N of attendants: 50/90 registered

Stakeholders: categories 1-5 as defined above

Topics: What is OPERAS and how to work with us, OPERAS services (amongst others D5.2, D4.1, D4.4)

Documentation/Reports: <https://operas-ger.hypotheses.org/821>

2. Workshops

Knowledge Infrastructures and Digital Governance. History, Challenges, Practices.

7-8 September 2020. Digital workshop.

OPERAS
open scholarly communication in the european
research area for social sciences and humanities

digital workshop

7 - 8 September 2020

Workshop organised by the OPERAS community

!

Register to receive Zoom link

Title: “**Knowledge Infrastructures and Digital Knowledge Workshop**”

Date: September 7–8, 2020

Number of attendants: 70

Stakeholders: researchers, infrastructure provider

Topics: theoretical and practical perspectives on issues around wide-ranging forms and aims of research infrastructures and the challenges digital governance faces

Documentation:

<https://www.c2dh.uni.lu/thinking/knowledge-infrastructures-and-digital-governance-workshop>

The [Knowledge Infrastructures and Digital Governance workshop](https://www.c2dh.uni.lu/thinking/knowledge-infrastructures-and-digital-governance-workshop) was held over two afternoons on 7 and 8 September 2020. It was organised for WP6 of the [OPERAS-P](https://www.c2dh.uni.lu/thinking/knowledge-infrastructures-and-digital-governance-workshop) project by Valérie Schafer and Lars Wieneke ([C²DH](https://www.c2dh.uni.lu/thinking/knowledge-infrastructures-and-digital-governance-workshop), University of Luxembourg), who co-lead Task 1 for reflection on new forms of governance, especially using digital technologies. The aim of this event, held online due to the ongoing public health situation, was to combine theoretical and practical perspectives on issues that are constantly developing as a result of the wide-ranging forms and aims of research infrastructures and the challenges facing digital governance – whether based on generic or specialised tools, on infrastructures that are proprietary or shared, open or closed, more or less decentralised, etc.

<https://www.c2dh.uni.lu/thinking/knowledge-infrastructures-and-digital-governance-workshop>

OPERAS-P Virtual Workshop

The Future of Scholarly Communication

February 24–26, 2021

operas-eu.org/news-and-events

Title: The Future of Scholarly Communication

Date: February 24–26, 2021

N of attendants: 340+

Stakeholders: researchers, publishers, librarians

Topics: digital tools, novel research approaches, interdisciplinary collaboration, Open Access, dissemination, business models, publishing practices, multilingualism, bibliodiversity

Documentation/Reports: <https://zenodo.org/communities/operaslab/?page=1&size=20>
operas-eu.org/4746

On the 24th–26th February Work Package 6 ‘Innovation’ in OPERAS-P held an online workshop/conference “The Future of Scholarly Communication”. During 3 days of seminars 341 participants explored digital transformation challenges in humanities and social sciences (SSH). The panels were linked to the question of how to effectively develop digital tools and services in order to apply novel research approaches, build interdisciplinary collaboration, raise the prestige of Open Access contributions and disseminate them outside academia.

The 3 Advocacy workshops and details can be found in section 10b in this report.

(1) Presentations at external conferences, workshops etc.

To reach out to different stakeholder groups and to a broader audience outside the community, OPERAS and results from the OPERAS-P project were presented at several external events and conferences. OPERAS has been present at significant international conferences such as LIBER, OpenScience, Pubmet, Charleston Library Conference, Digital Humanities Conference, ESOF2020 and many more.

In 2021:

- 24 June: Liber Conference Suzanne Dumouchel, CNRS (Huma-Num), France, Emilie Blotière, CNRS (Huma-Num), France, Judith Schulte, Max Weber Stiftung, Germany, Tiziana Lombardo, Net7: "From principles to reality: How OPERAS Research Infrastructure paves the way to Open Knowledge"
- 8 June: CNR Open Science training course, special sessions on research infrastructures, Alessia Smaniotto: "OPERAS: the research infrastructure for the humanities and social sciences" (in Italian)
- 18th and 20th May: NCP Training on Open Science, Science Communication and Citizen Science, Judith Schulte: "Communicating science to expert and non-expert audiences"
- 23 March: CNRS Medici network, online, Claire Clivaz: "The eTalks as a new scholarly writing and publication tool" (in French)

In 2020:

- 27 November, [NIE-INE final conference](#), University of Basel (CH), Claire Clivaz, "OPERAS: a new European Research Infrastructure"
- 10–13 November, DARIAH Annual Conference, Zagreb, Croatia, Workshop "Does Communication belong to Scholarly Primitives?" Erzsébeth Tóth-Czifra, Maciej Maryl, Jadranka Stojanovski, Claire Clivaz and Elisa Nury; Yoann Moranville, poster presentation OPERAS services <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4266181>
- 28 October, twinning of five National Points of contact, Claire Clivaz, "OPERAS: a new European Research Infrastructure"; organised by Euresearch-CH, <https://www.euresearch.ch/>
- 22 October, Swiss Annual Data Research Day (Geneva), Claire Clivaz and Elisa Nury, with Marta Błaszczczyńska, Michael Kaiser, Agata Morka, Valérie Schaefer, Jadranka Stojanovski, Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra, and in collaboration with Vera Chiquet : "Research Data as a New Model of Scholarly Writing in SSH"; slides and video : <https://doi.org/10.34847/nkl.f734kiqd> An article based on the talk is in submission.
- 21–24 September, OASPA2020, virtual, presentation: Elena Giglia, [slides](#), Pierre Mounier, [slides](#)
- 21 September, [2020 Workshop Multilingualism](#) (satellite event of the OASPA Conference 2020). Organised multi-institutionally by the Helsinki Initiative for Multilingualism, the Finnish Association for Academic Publication, the OPERAS Special Interest Group on Multilingualism, the European Network for the Evaluation of Research in Social and Human Sciences (ENRESSH), the Finnish Federation of Learned Societies and AEUP. Presentations from OPERAS: Delfim Leão, [slides](#), Suzanne Dumouchel, [slides](#).
- 16–18 September, PUBMET2020 conference, Zadar/virtual, OPERAS session, Jadranka Stojanovski, Pierre Mounier, Maciej Maryl, Suzanne Dumouchel, Krešimir Zauder, video: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=c_YBRXGDjoU&list=PLi0ZlYlnKSTu_5TNN1G3Mzvr9W38-jlDA&index=5
- 16–18 September, PUBMET2020 conference, Zadar/virtual, Maciej Maryl, Marta Błaszczczyńska, Agnieszka Szulińska, Paweł Rams: "[The Case for an Inclusive Scholarly Communication Infrastructure for Social Sciences and Humanities](#)".
- 10–11 September 2020, "[Virtual Research Environments and Ancient Manuscripts](#)", the first SNSF [MARK16 conference](#), organized online from Lausanne (CH) by Claire

Clivaz and Garrick Allen. Two OPERAS invited papers: Suzanne Dumouchel and Yoann Moranville, "[Increasing impact of SSH research: Use cases of OPERAS services in the EOSC](#)"; Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra, "[Rethinking text, techné and tenure-VREs as an evaluation and peer-review challenge in Humanities](#)", with an article accepted for publication (see below).

- 7–8 September 2020, "Knowledge infrastructures and digital governance. History, challenges, practices.", OPERAS-P workshop Programme: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4260>
- 5–9 July 2020, ESOF2020 - Euroscience Open Forum, Trieste, Suzanne Dumouchel, panel discussion
- 19–21 June, CERN-UNIGO Workshop, Pierre Mounier
- 9–10 June, SIB days conference, virtual, CH, presentations by Claire, Elisa, Vera, Marta and Erzsébet with DH+/ Core-IT SIB colleagues, poster: "Open Science and Humanities: research data management"
- 2–6 March, DHD2020, Paderborn, Judith Schulte: poster presentation of the discovery service
- 19–20 March, Open Science Conference, Berlin, Elena Giglia (paper with ALLEA), Judith Schulte: Poster Presentation of the Discovery service
- 23–24 January, GO FAIR annual meeting, Hamburg, by Elena Giglia and Arnaud Gingold

In 2019:

- 18–19, November, Journées Nationales de la Science Ouverte, Paris, France, Pierre Mounier with Vanessa Proudman
- 6–8, November, Charleston Library Conference, Charleston, SC, USA, Rupert Gatti, Eelco Ferwerda
- 14, October, JISC Workshop on metrics, London, UK, Pierre Mounier
- 1 October, Public presentation of OPERAS at OPERAS-P kickoff meeting, Warsaw, Pierre Mounier, Suzanne Dumouchel, Paulin Ribbe
<https://operas.hypotheses.org/2804>
- 18-19 September, PUBMET2019 conference, Zadar, Croatia, Paulin Ribbe, Pierre Mounier, "[OPERAS: Shaping a Distributed Research Infrastructure Advocating for Open Scholarly Communication](#)", [slides](#)
- 5 September 2019, HIRMEOS Project Final Review. Luxembourg. European Commission. Pierre Mounier, Eelco Ferwerda, Margo Bargheer, Paulin Ribbe.
- 9-12 July, DH 2019 Digital Humanities Conference, Utrecht, Netherlands, Pierre Mounier, Suzanne Dumouchel, presentations

c) Communication activities of partner institutions etc., Press Release

OPERAS members and project partners were asked to actively participate in external communication. Some of their activities are listed here as examples:

- 24 July 2019, blog post, OpenEdition, "CO-OPERAS IN – Winner of the ANR open science call for projects on research data" : <https://oep.hypotheses.org/2268>

- 12 September 2019, blog post, OpenEdition, "OPERAS receives funding to develop its infrastructure and services" : <https://oep.hypotheses.org/2278>
- 23 September 2019, press release, "EU bewilligt mit OPERAS-P den Ausbau der europäischen Forschungsinfrastruktur für die Geistes- und Sozialwissenschaften", Max Weber Stiftung
<https://www.maxweberstiftung.de/presse/aktuelles-presse/einzelansicht-pressemeldung/detail/News/eu-bewilligt-mit-operas-p-den-ausbau-der-europaeischen-forschungsinfrastruktur-fuer-die-geistes-und-sozialwissenschaften.html>
- 10 October 2019, internal information letter of SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics "OPERAS-P H2020"; sent to 800 SIB members in Switzerland.
- 3 December 2019, news article, "Workshop sobre dados de investigação com incidência dos princípios FAIR", UC Open Science, Coimbra University
<https://noticias.uc.pt/universo-uc/workshop-sobre-dados-de-investigacao-com-incidencia-dos-principios-fair/>
- 9 January 2020, press release, "Forschungsinfrastruktur OPERAS gibt sich eine Rechtsform", Max Weber Stiftung
<https://www.maxweberstiftung.de/presse/aktuelles-presse/einzelansicht-pressemeldung/detail/News/forschungsinfrastruktur-operas-gibt-sich-eine-rechtsform.html>
- 09 January 2020, blog post, OpenEdition, "OPERAS Founded International Association" : <https://oep.hypotheses.org/2426>
- 10 March 2020, news article, "Πρόσκληση συμμετοχής της ερευνητικής κοινότητας στην έρευνα του OPERAS για την επιστημονική επικοινωνία στις ΑΚΕ", National Documentation Centre (EKT) <http://blog.openaccess.gr/?s=OPERAS-P>
- 17 March 2020, blog post, OpenEdition, "Call for Researchers – OPERAS Survey on SSH Scholarly Communication" : <https://oep.hypotheses.org/2499>
- 05 May 2020, blog post, OpenEdition, "'Beyond Covid-19': call for participation" : <https://oep.hypotheses.org/2533>
- 15 May 2020, news article, „OPERAS uruchamia bibliografię *Beyond COVID-19*: Zaproszenie do udziału w projekcie", IBL PAN
<https://biuletynpolonistyczny.pl/pl/articles/operas-uruchamia-bibliografie-beyond-covid-19-zaproszenie-do-udzialu-w-projekcie.184/details>
- 15 April 2020, newsletter, "OAPEN launches on a new platform", OAPEN
<https://us4.campaign-archive.com/?u=314fa411ba5eaaee7244c95e1&id=e9bc5d6a0c>
- 5 April 2020, blog, "OAPEN launches on new platform", OAPEN
<https://oapen.hypotheses.org/74>
- 8 June 2020, news article, "OPERAS selects members for the Scientific Advisory Committee", UC Open Science, Coimbra University
<https://www.uc.pt/en/openscience/article?key=a-3101b0fe96>
- 9 June 2020, Call for Members, "OPERAS Scientific Advisory Committee – zaproszenie do udziału w naborze", IBL PAN
<https://ibl.waw.pl/pl/operas-scientific-advisory-committee-zaproszenie-do-udzialu-w-naborze>,
- 22 June 2020, news article, "International research gathers impressions about multilingualism in academic communication", UC Open Science, Coimbra University
<https://www.uc.pt/en/openscience/article?key=a-83fd7acae6>
- 01 July 2020, news article, "OPERAS consortium welcomes new members", UC Open Science, Coimbra University
<https://www.uc.pt/en/openscience/article?key=a-6b4e7acbf7>

- 8 July 2020, news article, "'Beyond Covid-19': open library is accepting contributions", UC Open Science, Coimbra University
<https://www.uc.pt/en/openscience/article?key=a-aa69461c2e>
- 27 July 2020, Diamond OA Survey invitation, "Pomóż OPERAS poznać czasopisma i platformy otwartego dostępu, które są bezpłatne dla czytelników i autorów", IBL PAN
<https://biuletynpolonistyczny.pl/pl/articles/pomoz-operas-poznac-czasopisma-i-platfor-my-otwartego-dostepu-ktore-sa-bezplatne-dla-czytelnikow-i-autorow,188/details>,
- 28 July 2020, news article, "Diamond model: research about journals and open access platforms", UC Open Science, Coimbra University
<https://www.uc.pt/en/openscience/article?key=a-457c9134ef>
- 07 September 2020, blog post, OpenEdition, "Help us get to know the open access journals and platforms that don't charge author-fees" :
<https://oep.hypotheses.org/2560>
- 8 October 2020 news article, " OPERAS 2020 Conference receives registrations", UC Open Science, Coimbra University
<https://www.uc.pt/en/openscience/article?key=a-2bc7f7f79c>
- 09 October 2020, blog post, OpenEdition, "OPERAS Conference "Opening up Social Sciences and Humanities in Europe: From Promises to Reality": registration is open!"
- 12 October 2020, newsletter article, "How EGI Supports Social Sciences and Humanities"
<https://www.egi.eu/about/newsletters/how-egi-supports-the-social-sciences-and-humanities-community/>
- 12 October 2020, news article, "How EGI support social sciences and humanities", EGI
<https://www.egi.eu/about/newsletters/how-egi-supports-the-social-sciences-and-humanities-community/>
- 16 October 2020, workshop report, "Knowledge Infrastructures and Digital Governance Workshop", University of Luxembourg
<https://www.c2dh.uni.lu/thinking/knowledge-infrastructures-and-digital-governance-workshop>
- 20 October 2020, conference invitation, "OPERAS Conference *Opening up Social Sciences and Humanities in Europe: From Promises to Reality*", IBL PAN
<https://biuletynpolonistyczny.pl/pl/events/operas-conference-opening-up-social-sciences-and-humanities-in-europe-from-promises-to-reality,2259/details>,
- 31 October 2020, news article, "Διεθνές συνέδριο για την Ανοικτή Επιστήμη και την ακαδημαϊκή επικοινωνία στις Ανθρωπιστικές και Κοινωνικές Επιστήμες", National Documentation Centre (EKT) <http://www.ekt.gr/el/news/25008>
- 18 December 2020, newsletter, "DOAB Season's Greeting", DOAB:
<https://us4.campaign-archive.com/?u=314fa411ba5eaaee7244c95e1&id=b430b754f4>
- 22 December 2020, news article, "Η Ανοικτή Επιστήμη κερδίζει συνεχώς έδαφος στην Ευρώπη", National Documentation Centre (EKT) <http://www.ekt.gr/el/news/25140>
- 28 January 2021, news article, "Διαδικτυακό Forum για την ανοικτή επιστημονική επικοινωνία στις Ανθρωπιστικές & Κοινωνικές Επιστήμες, από OPERAS & PKP", National Documentation Centre (EKT) <http://www.ekt.gr/el/news/25358>
- 8 February 2021 news article, "PKP community forum discusses social sciences and humanities in Europe", UC Open Science, Coimbra University
<https://www.uc.pt/en/openscience/article?key=a-231a519d20>
- 15 February 2021, conference invitation, Konferencja OPERAS *The Future of Scholarly Communication*", IBL PAN

<https://biuletynpolonistyczny.pl/pl/events/konferencja-operas-the-future-of-scholarly-communication,2334/details>

- 16 February 2021, news article, "The future of scholarly communication is discussed in OPERAS-P workshop", UC Open Science, Coimbra University
<https://www.uc.pt/en/openscience/article?key=a-c00b0d21d6>
- 17 February 2021 press release, "The Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB) relaunches on the open source DSpace platform", DOAB:
<https://www.doabooks.org/en/doab/article/doab-relaunches-on-the-open-source-dspace-platform>
- 17 February 2021, newsletter, "The Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB) relaunches on the open source DSpace platform", DOAB
<https://us4.campaign-archive.com/?u=314fa411ba5eaaee7244c95e1&id=8d91ce0609>
- 5 March 2021, news article, "Report on Open Access Books and libraries in Europe is released", UC Open Science, Coimbra University
<https://www.uc.pt/en/openscience/article?key=a-08c6e05258>
- 9 April 2021, news article, "Workshop discusses OA journals and the Ibero-American publishers landscape", Coimbra University Article disseminating the SIGs (Advocacy and Multilingualism) workshop/National Node event Portugal -
<https://www.uc.pt/en/openscience/article?key=a-5e6790c293>
- 5 March 2021, survey invitation, (OPERAS Business Models), "Ankieta OPERAS dla wydawnictw na temat książek w otwartym dostępie (open access)", IBL PAN
<https://biuletynpolonistyczny.pl/pl/articles/ankieta-operas-dla-wydawnictw-na-temat-ksiazek-w-otwartym-dostepie-open-access,202/details>,
<https://ibl.waw.pl/pl/ankieta-operas-dla-wydawnictw-na-temat-ksiazek-w-otwartym-dostepie-open-access>,
<https://ibl.waw.pl/pl/operas-business-models-survey-on-open-access-books>
- March 2021, OAPEN Spotlight Post, workshop invitation, : "Workshop: Innovative business models for open access book publishing in Europe", OAPEN
<https://oopen.org/oopen/article/9340766-workshop-innovative-business-models-for-open-access-book-publishing-in-europe>
- 9 March 2021, conference summary, "Konferencja OPERAS *The Future of Scholarly Communication*", IBL PAN
<https://biuletynpolonistyczny.pl/pl/events/summary/konferencja-operas-the-future-of-scholarly-communication,2334/details>,
- 15 March 2021, news article: "Survey investigates collaborative publishing models for Open Access books", UC Open Science, Coimbra University
<https://www.uc.pt/en/openscience/article?key=a-f2880056fd>
- 25 March 2021, newsletter:, "2021: ERC, Plan S & community engagement", DOAB
<https://us4.campaign-archive.com/?u=314fa411ba5eaaee7244c95e1&id=5691d8a9d2>
- 28 April 2021, news article, "Διαδικτυακή ημερίδα «Οικοδομώντας κοινότητες για την προώθηση της Ανοικτής Ακαδημαϊκής Επικοινωνίας στις Ανθρωπιστικές και Κοινωνικές Επιστήμες»", National Documentation Centre (EKT),
<http://www.ekt.gr/el/events/25792>
- 15 June, 2021, blog post, "New Models of Scholarly Writing. DH+ contribution to OPERAS-P", Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics
<https://claireclivaz.hypotheses.org/2369>

- 17 June 2021, blog post, OpenEdition, "Workshop : « Soutenir la communication ouverte en SHS à l'échelle française et européenne : l'infrastructure OPERAS » – 28 juin 2021" : <https://leo.hypotheses.org/17647>

i) Website operas-eu.org

The OPERAS website was newly developed within the project: [operas-eu.org](https://www.operas-eu.org). It is hosted by the University of Torino and edited by Max Weber Stiftung. The website is used to generally communicate the main information about the RI and the project and disseminate project results. It offers viewers the possibility to get a general overview about the RI and is regularly updated. It is aimed at all target groups and a general audience.

OPERAS
open scholarly communication in the european research area for social sciences and humanities

About ▾ Special Interest Groups ▾ Services ▾ Projects ▾ News & Events ▾ International Partnerships ▾ Q

OPERAS
open scholarly communication in the european research area for social sciences and humanities

[Read more](#)

OPERAS: How to
How to join OPERAS? Get part of the network!
[Read more](#)

Voices from the community
What's going on in the OPERAS community?
[Watch videos from the community](#)

Services
Service descriptions Discovery, Certification, Metrics, Publishing Service Portal, Research for Society, Future
[Read more](#)

Bookshelf
All publications in the OPERAS community @Zenodo
[Read more](#)

Need more?
Press material, Logos, Flyer, Newsletter
[Check our material](#)

Work with us
Contact information
[Read more](#)

OPERAS - PKP - Forum
Discuss within the European Community

[Forum](#)

Starting Page

Within the menu structure there is information on "OPERAS in a nutshell", the different Assemblies, the members, and the coordination team. Then there is a place for the OPERAS Special Interest Groups to present themselves and their results. The main menu point is reserved for the different projects belonging to the RI, OPERAS-P for example <https://www.operas-eu.org/projects/operas-p/>.

There is also a news section, published on the OPERAS blog and an event calendar, where all OPERAS events are listed.

The following metrics were done with the tool Matomo. The first overview shows the numbers from June 2020 to June 2021.

Visitors from June 2020 to June 2021

As the extract from the page views show, the biggest interest for visitors on the website is the general information about the OPERAS RI. The main traffic is on the starting page and about OPERAS and the general information about the projects and Special Interest Groups.

PAGE URL	PAGEVIEWS	UNIQUE PAGEVIEWS	BOUNCE RATE	AVG. TIME ON PAGE	EXIT RATE	AVG. PAGE LOAD TIME
/index	3,511	2,969	55%	00:00:40	63%	7.69s
about	2,863	2,339	58%	00:01:21	41%	1.92s
projects	1,321	1,117	66%	00:01:26	72%	8.57s
special-interest-groups	957	789	75%	00:01:01	58%	2.75s
services	921	748	57%	00:01:12	43%	2.67s
news-and-events	613	478	69%	00:00:55	59%	2.18s
special-interest-group-living-book	610	326	42%	00:01:28	33%	2.52s
operas-newsletter	348	300	85%	00:00:50	82%	2.32s
event	115	96	67%	00:00:59	83%	2.14s
contact-2	93	80	85%	00:00:49	49%	8.02s
bookshelf	93	73	62%	00:01:45	49%	2.54s
international-partnerships	76	63	47%	00:01:31	46%	3.81s
voices-from-the-community	52	50	83%	00:01:38	44%	5.51s
special-interest-group-living-book-advocacy-2	82	27	23%	00:03:51	41%	2.88s
design-study	29	24	73%	00:00:12	88%	3.12s

This overview shows that generating a general OPERAS website was necessary. This makes it easy for the audience to get an overview of OPERAS and its development and actions.

ii) OPERAS Blog

After the launch of the website in June 2020 the OPERAS blog operas.hypotheses.org was restructured. The blog contains the main news items from the RI, the different OPERAS projects and the network/community directly published in post form. Newly established is a community section for posts from the community. In the blog, short summaries of workshops and publications were disseminated and new developments etc. can be directly addressed to a large audience. After the blog restructure, it is possible to find different categories in the menu to sort blog posts. To disseminate the blog posts, each one was accompanied by a tweet and posts on Facebook and LinkedIn.

The number of visits to the blog have been continuously growing the last few years, increasing by more than 60% during the OPERAS-P project. The metrics source used for the blog is Awstats. This tool differs from Matomo in the efficiency of the bot detection method and shows higher numbers than Matomo.

- 56,107.0 visits in 2021(only first 5 months)
- 132,782.0 visits in 2020
- 84,275.0 visits in 2019
- 68,546.0 visits in 2018
- 21,355.0 visits in 2017

Summary					
Reported period	Year 2021				
First visit	01 Jan 2021 - 00:04				
Last visit	19 Jun 2021 - 01:54				
	Unique visitors	Number of visits	Pages	Hits	Bandwidth
Viewed traffic *	<= 18,903	70,997	143,160	145,213	7.83 GB
	Exact value not available in 'Year' view	(3.75 visits/visitor)	(2.01 Pages/Visit)	(2.04 Hits/Visit)	(115.66 KB/Visit)
Not viewed traffic *			212,163	230,369	6.37 GB

Month	Unique visitors	Number of visits	Pages	Hits	Bandwidth
Jan 2021	1,995	9,225	19,165	19,442	1017.81 MB
Feb 2021	4,033	13,111	27,468	27,958	1.81 GB
Mar 2021	4,433	14,958	30,805	31,158	1.90 GB
Apr 2021	3,474	13,311	25,880	26,258	1.53 GB
May 2021	2,679	12,512	24,413	24,764	946.84 MB
Jun 2021	2,289	7,880	15,429	15,633	681.48 MB
Jul 2021	0	0	0	0	0
Aug 2021	0	0	0	0	0
Sep 2021	0	0	0	0	0
Oct 2021	0	0	0	0	0
Nov 2021	0	0	0	0	0
Dec 2021	0	0	0	0	0
Total	18,903	70,997	143,160	145,213	7.83 GB

Numbers from June 21, 2021.

Summary					
Reported period	Year 2020				
First visit	01 Jan 2020 - 00:08				
Last visit	31 Dec 2020 - 23:59				
	Unique visitors	Number of visits	Pages	Hits	Bandwidth
Viewed traffic *	<= 46,866 Exact value not available in 'Year' view	132,782 (2.83 visits/visitor)	277,263 (2.08 Pages/Visit)	281,368 (2.11 Hits/Visit)	14.86 GB (117.38 KB/Visit)
Not viewed traffic *			314,954	359,040	8.05 GB

Month	Unique visitors	Number of visits	Pages	Hits	Bandwidth
Jan 2020	3,127	8,289	15,257	15,493	694.70 MB
Feb 2020	3,674	8,996	17,569	17,826	808.24 MB
Mar 2020	4,964	11,586	21,271	21,639	1.10 GB
Apr 2020	4,159	10,822	19,651	19,993	1.05 GB
May 2020	4,372	10,400	25,485	26,051	1.75 GB
Jun 2020	5,235	12,249	33,109	33,633	1.67 GB
Jul 2020	4,415	12,788	28,826	29,147	1.45 GB
Aug 2020	3,981	12,554	27,534	27,748	1.35 GB
Sep 2020	4,680	13,655	26,797	27,094	1.53 GB
Oct 2020	3,270	11,599	21,209	21,531	1.29 GB
Nov 2020	2,655	10,106	19,774	20,203	1.19 GB
Dec 2020	2,334	9,738	20,781	21,010	1.03 GB
Total	46,866	132,782	277,263	281,368	14.86 GB

As the metrics show, the OPERAS blog is the channel with the biggest audience. They show that, even though the website was established in June 2020, the audience for the blog grows continuously or stays on a high level. The highest number of visitors occurred in March 2021 with 14,985 viewers in one month, which corresponds to the time that the results from the diamond Open Access study, a project with several other partners coordinated by OPERAS, were published (<https://operas.hypotheses.org/4579>). All in all 66 blog posts were published on the OPERAS blog within the time of the project, not all results of the OPERAS-P project, but belonging to the OPERAS RI and its community. This shows that the strategy to highlight OPERAS within its active and growing community was successful, and OPERAS is getting a higher reputation and growing audience. The most successful post about a survey on Open Access diamond journals translated into several languages: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4205>. Very successful as well was the programme for the highly requested OPERAS-P WP6 workshop (<https://operas.hypotheses.org/4512>).

List of OPERAS blog posts:

- 16 July 2019, CO-OPERAS IN Kick-off: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/2697>
- 18 July 2019, OPERAS signed the Helsinki Initiative on Multilingualism: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/2718>
- 24 July 2019, CO-OPERAS IN - Winner of the ANR Open Science call for projects on research data: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/2732>
- 9 September 2019, A Plan S for academic books: Report on EASSH - OPERAS Roundtable: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/2750>
- 11 September 2019, OPERAS receives funding to develop its infrastructure and services: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/2774>
- 17 September 2019, OPERA's answers to the expert group for Open Science of the European Commission: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/2785>
- 25 September 2019, Invitation to the OPERAS-P launch: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/2804>
- 10 October 2019, Launch of TRIPLE, the European discovery solution dedicated to SSH resources: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/2840>
- 22 October 2019, New technical coordinator: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/2851>
- 28 October 2019, DARIAH and OPERAS join forces to make Open Science a reality in the arts, humanities and social sciences: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/2863>
- 8 November 2019, OPERAS created coordination team: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/2910>
- 27 November 2019, Invitation to the TRIPLE Kick-off meeting: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/3007>
- 10 December 2019, OPERAS members (OAPEN and PKP) and OPERAS service (DOAB) are supported by SCOSS funding: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/3063>
- 12 December 2019, Save the date: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/3142>
- 9 January 2020, OPERAS founded international association: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/3182>
- 20 February 2020, Post-publication open peer review experiment: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/3815>
- 2 March 2020, Call for researchers - survey on SSH scholarly communication: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/3932>

- 3 March 2020, Question to the OPERAS community - the OPERAS governance study: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/3877>
- 12 March 2020, Humanities and data: listening to the communities on the path towards FAIRness: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4010>
- 27 March 2020, Postponed: OPERAS annual conference to take place 2-4 November 2020: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4045>
- 1 April 2020, New OPERAS Newsletter: Marcy 2020: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4039>
- 7 April 2020, Help us find out more about scholarly communication practices: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4065>
- 8 April 2020, Become part of the network: join OPERAS: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4067>
- 15 April 2020, OAPEN launches on new platform: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4073>
- 5 May 2020, OPERAS launches "Beyond Covid-19": call for participation: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4084>
- 6 May 2020, TRIPLE launches user research survey: call for participation: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4094>
- 8 May 2020, Call for contributions: knowledge infrastructures and digital governance. History, challenges, practices: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/3850>
- 15 May 2020, Modern tools and ancient documents: conference "Virtual Research Environments and Ancient Manuscripts" - SNSF MARK16 project: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4112>
- 20 May 2020, SPARC Europe Survey: Scoping the OA and OS infrastructure (OSI) landscape in Europe: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4119>
- 3 June 2020, Call for members - OPERAS scientific advisory committee: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4129>
- 10 June 2020, OPERAS and partners selected by cOAlition S for study on OA Diamond: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4141>
- 25 June 2020, TRIPLE: Behind the scenes #1: Suzanne Dumouchel: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4147>
- 26 June 2020, Multilingualism in scholarly communication: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4168>
- 26 June 2020, OPERAS welcomes new members: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4179>
- 29 June 2020, New OPERAS Newsletter: June 2020: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4197>
- 22 July 2020, Help us get to know the open access journals and platforms that are free of charge for readers and authors: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4205>
- 28 July 2020, Programme available: "Knowledge infrastructures and digital governance. History, challenges, practices." 7-8 September 2020: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4260>
- 7 August 2020, Library support for Open Access books workshop: the German perspective: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4275>
- 7 September 2020, Survey on Open Access diamond journals: 2000 contributions already. Do we have yours?: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4289>

- 8 September 2020, Invitation to the launch of the Open Access Books Network: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4300>
- 9 September 2020, PUBMET2020, 16-18 September 2020: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4303>
- 14 September 2020, OPERAS has signed the “Passenger Pigeon Manifesto”: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4345>
- 15 September 2020, TRIPLE: Behind the scenes #2 Paula Forbes: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4318>
- 25 September 2020, OPERAS conference coming soon: 2-4 November 2020: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4375>
- 6 October 2020, OPERAS looking for research assistance on OA Diamond study: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4387>
- 6 October 2020, New OPERAS Newsletter: September 2020: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4391>
- 25 November 2020: TRIPLE: Behind the scenes #3: Francesca Di Donato: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4404>
- 27 November 2020: One week left before the CO-OPERAS and TRIPLE session at GOFAIR symposium: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4432>
- 27 November 2020: Report on the OPERAS workshop “How to fill the information gap: Open Access for the social sciences and humanities”: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4435>
- 9 December 2020, TRIPLE: Behind the scenes #4: mateusz Franczak: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4420>
- 11 December 2020, Start of OPERAS-GER: First national node of OPERAS in Germany: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4453>
- 2 February 2021, OPERAS and PKP join forces to launch “European Community in SSH” forum: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4488>
- 4 February 2021, COESO kick-off meeting: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4493>
- 9 February 2021, OPERAS welcomes Niels Stern as a member in the Executive Assembly: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4500>
- 12 February 2021, The future of scholarly communication - OPERAS-P Workshop: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4512>
- 15 February 2021, Suzanne Dumouchel has been elected to become one of 8 directors of the EOSC association: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4544>
- 17 February 2021, DOAB successfully relaunches the OPERAS certification service on the open source DSpace platform: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4552>
- 22 February 2021, New OPERAS Newsletter: February 2021: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4566>
- 26 February 2021, For a change: let’s Make a Change! OPERAS Survey on collaborative models for Open Access books: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4571>
- 9 March 2021, OA Diamond Journals study completed: report emphasizes diversity and sustainable pathways for diamond Open Access: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4579>
- 15 March 2021, Survey on citizen science funding in the social sciences and humanities: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4592>
- 25 March 2021, Workshop7 April 2021: Innovative business models for OA book publishing in Europe: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4602>

- 9 April 2021, Publishers and publishing stances: a contribution to multilingualism and bibliodiversity: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4651>
- 15 April 2021, Join the 1st TRIPLE ThatCamp on 11 May 2021: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4637>
- 21 April 2021, OPERAS-P and OASPA workshop report: innovative business models for OA books: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4651>
- 30 April 2021, New OPERAS Newsletter: April 2021: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4674>

d) Social Media Activities

The social media activities were very important for the OPERAS communication as they allow fast communication and facilitate a two-way conversation. The goals of the OPERAS social media presence were to:

- reach a broader audience than through more traditional dissemination activities
- update the OPERAS community, build a strong base of engaged followers
- gain more attention for the OPERAS community
- drive more traffic to the OPERAS blog and website
- engage with user communities/respond to queries
- monitor and improve OPERAS' reputation

To be sure to reach out to the different audiences in the different countries 3 channels were operated:

- Twitter (social network, where researchers are present)
- Facebook (informative social network)
- LinkedIn (professional social network)

Especially the twitter accounts offered the possibility for all OPERAS partners to take an active part in the conversations. The OPERAS communication lead encouraged the consortium to use #OPERAS and @OPERASEU for relevant posts on their own social media channels. Many tweets from consortium partners and members were retweeted with the OPERAS account, so show the community.

Twitter Metrics @OPERASEU from June 29,2021

Twitter Tweet Impressions from June 29,2021

As the diagram above shows, the number of Twitter Followers has been growing constantly during the time of the project. The @OPERASEU Twitter channel has received 938 new followers in the time of the project and the number of tweet impressions has been continuously growing with bigger deviations within the different months. It received especially high interest during the OPERAS2020 conference in November 2020 and the OPERAS-P WP6 workshop in February 2021.

Some top-tweets on OPERAS-P results and examples of tweets of OPERAS members:

<https://twitter.com/OPERASEU/status/1365268828721213441>

Impressions	14.446
Interaktionen insgesamt	124
Detailerweiterungen	34
Link-Klicks	28
Retweets	27
„Gefällt mir“-Angaben	21
Medieninteraktionen	6
Profilklicks	5
Hashtag-Klicks	3

<https://t.co/glk720fbY0>

OPERAS @OPERASEU · Feb 12

Join us and discuss with us: the virtual #workshop "The Future of Scholarly Communication" takes place from 24 to 26 February. Find the program and registration here: operas-eu.org/4512

#scholcomm #SSH @IBLPAN #ResearchimpactEU #humanities #socialsciences #bibliodiversity

Marta Błaszczyszka and 8 others

Impressions	30,701
Total engagements	397
Link clicks	144
Detail expands	69
Retweets	62
Media engagements	56
Likes	50
Profile clicks	13
Hashtag clicks	3

<https://twitter.com/OPERASEU/status/1313777577245446144>

OPERAS @OPERASEU · Oct 7, 2020

[#OPERAS2020] Registration is open: "Opening up Social Sciences and Humanities: From Promises to Reality", November 2-4, 2020, virtual event. Registration is free at operas2020.com #openscience #openaccess #scholcomm #SSH #HSS #OA #researchimpactEU #EU

OpenEdition News and 5 others

Impressions	15,337
Total engagements	378
Link clicks	96
Detail expands	84
Media engagements	65
Retweets	58
Likes	56
Profile clicks	13
Hashtag clicks	5
Replies	1

Consortium/Member-Tweets

<https://twitter.com/maciejmaryl/status/1365278738544549889>

Du hast retweetet

Maciej Maryl @maciejmaryl · 26. Feb. #OPERASLab in numbers

- 3 days
- 6 sessions
- 13 presenters
- 18 experts
- 270 minutes
- 341 participants
- 1 and only @OPERASEU

operas.hypotheses.org/4512

Du und 9 weitere Personen

<https://twitter.com/OPERASEU/status/1364506036250542082>

The overview of the period from May 20 to June 22, 2021 shows a growing number of public interest.

Month	Tweets	Follower	Mentions	Visits	Likes	Retweets	Impressions
Jun-19	18,00	35,00	38,00	246,00	134,00	64,00	33400,00
Jul-19	5,00	17,00	10,00	56,00	74,00	37,00	20900,00
Aug-19	0,00	15,00	10,00	25,00	1,00	2,00	5953,00
Sep-19	9,00	19,00	47,00	102,00	88,00	70,00	23300,00
Oct-19	17,00	54,00	92,00	223,00	165,00	113,00	36000,00
Nov-19	7,00	41,00	33,00	179,00	93,00	64,00	22900,00
Dec-19	11,00	22,00	46,00	248,00	113,00	60,00	22900,00
Jan-20	10,00	34,00	43,00	243,00	125,00	62,00	30000,00
Feb-20	7,00	38,00	72,00	263,00	99,00	99,00	31300,00
Mar-20	21,00	68,00	70,00	439,00	178,00	237,00	87900,00
Apr-20	15,00	34,00	36,00	316,00	114,00	101,00	51500,00
May-20	14,00	31,00	21,00	329,00	93,00	120,00	35000,00
Jun-20	22,00	58,00	57,00	579,00	216,00	213,00	57500,00

Jul-20	6,00	46,00	46,00	354,00	73,00	65,00	28100,00
Aug-20	6,00	20,00	32,00	240,00	77,00	78,00	29500,00
Sep-20	43,00	53,00	100,00	651,00	344,00	266,00	81400,00
Oct-20	16,00	45,00	46,00	973,00	187,00	174,00	59200,00
Nov-20	80,00	52,00	90,00	934,00	367,00	222,00	104000,00
Dec-20	6,00	23,00	16,00	532,00	71,00	29,00	18300,00
Jan-21	3,00	62,00	32,00	535,00	12,00	16,00	7070,00
Feb-21	14,00	60,00	120,00	1875,00	236,00	159,00	75100,00
Mar-21	14,00	40,00	77,00	1144,00	146,00	137,00	56400,00
Apr-21	24,00	45,00	84,00	1334,00	166,00	121,00	47600,00
May-21	20,00	36,00	102,00	1515,00	132,00	82,00	38800,00
Jun-21	40,00	52,00	107,00	2000,00	362,00	254,00	77800,00
per month	17,12	40,00	57,08	373,35	106,42	138,83	41002,79
for project time	410,00	965,00	1389,00	15089,00	3532,00	2781,00	1048423,00

Twitter Metrics from June 17, 2021 (numbers for June 2021 are not complete).

The consortium of the OPERAS-P project has been very active spreading surveys and news of the RI and the project, and they used the social media accounts of their home institution or they have their own personal/profession accounts. This activity can be read within the numbers of retweets, mentions and impressions. To give a detailed impression of the communication activities examples listed in the appendix.

LinkedIn and Facebook

Both the LinkedIn and Facebook accounts were used to spread the blog post. Around 80 posts were spread on each of the platforms. The OPERAS page on LinkedIn has 169 followers as of June 2021. LinkedIn Analytics, in the middle of May 2021 to the middle of June 2021

The OPERAS community on Facebook has received 149 likes and 184 followers in June 2021. OPERAS reached around 20 to 34 people with one post on Facebook.

LinkedIn Metrics, June 2021

Twitter was chosen as the most important social media network. Twitter arose as the main channel to address OPERAS stakeholders, such as researchers, publishers, research infrastructures and libraries. Therefore, the most effort was spent to build up the OPERAS Twitter community and OPERAS has by far the most followers and impressions here. But as the analysis of visitors on the website shows, more visitors come directly from Facebook to the OPERAS website than from twitter. Therefore, it seems useful to continue sharing some posts on Facebook as well. Only four viewers came in one year from LinkedIn, and the number of followers stayed around 168. Therefore, the aims for this platform have not been reached. So it might be reasonable to close the LinkedIn account in the future and focus the social media activities only on Twitter and Facebook or to define a new strategy for the LinkedIn Account and use it more to make connections between different institutions and researchers in the OPERAS role as a coordinator and not to bring messages on posts anymore. This needs to be highly monitored and reviewed for future projects.

e) Newsletter

The OPERAS Newsletter, managed by Max Weber Stiftung, is GDPR-compliant with a double-opt-in procedure to subscribe and unsubscribe on the OPERAS website.

OPERAS Newsletter

The newsletter keeps you updated about the OPERAS Research Infrastructure, its ongoing projects (COESO, OPERAS-P, TRIPLE, Study on OA Diamond, OPERAS-GER), the CO-OPERAS GoFAIR Implementation Network, its international cooperation, our community and upcoming events.

Find out what's going on in the OPERAS community and follow our newsletter! You can find the latest newsletter [here](#).

Subscribe for the OPERAS Newsletter:

Enter your e-mail address

I've read the [data protection policy](#) and accept it.

Unsubscribe here:

Enter your e-mail address

operas-eu.org/operas-newsletter/

During the time of the project, 5 quarterly newsletters were sent out beginning in March 2020. In addition to distributing the newsletter by email, links to the newsletter are provided on the OPERAS blog and website to generate more viewers. The April 2021 newsletter was sent out to 251 subscribers and was opened by an even bigger audience of 373 viewers.

The newsletter updated a broader audience and the OPERAS members and consortia about the OPERAS Research Infrastructure, its ongoing projects (COESO, OPERAS-P, TRIPLE, Study on OA Diamond, OPERAS-GER), the CO-OPERAS GoFAIR Implementation Network, its international cooperation, our community and upcoming events. Therefore, the newsletters were longer html-documents, giving an overview about all activities around the RI. They were all linked on an archive page on the website:

<https://www.operas-eu.org/operas-newsletter-archive/>

- OPERAS Newsletter [April 2021](#), send out to 251 subscribers, seen by 373 viewers
- OPERAS Newsletter [February 2021](#), send out to 210 subscribers, seen by 327 viewers
- OPERAS Newsletter [September 2020](#), send out to 162 subscribers, seen by 539 viewers
- OPERAS Newsletter [June 2020](#), send out to 142 subscribers, read by 288 people
- OPERAS Newsletter [March 2020](#), send out to 122 subscribers, read by 605 people

OPERAS Newsletter

April 2021

Welcome to the OPERAS Newsletter! The newsletter keeps you updated about the OPERAS Research Infrastructure, its ongoing projects (COESO, OPERAS-P, TRIPLE Study on OA Diamond, OPERAS-GER), the CO-OPERAS GoFAIR Implementation Network, its international cooperation, our community and upcoming events. Find out what's going on in the OPERAS community and follow our newsletter!

For the upcoming month OPERAS has a full schedule of online events. Check our Save the Date section and our event page.

If you do not want to receive this newsletter anymore, please unsubscribe [here](#) or send an e-mail to communication@operas-eu.org.

Content

OPERAS Research Infrastructure

- Publishers and Publishing Stances (event recap)
- OPERAS Welcomes New Members
- More OPERAS News in a Nutshell

OPERAS-P Project

- Innovative business models for open access book publishing in Europe (event recap)
- Project results: New Publications

COESO

- Survey on Citizen Science funding has been concluded
- COESO's Communication and Dissemination Strategy has been published
- COESO's website and Twitter channel go live

TRIPLE Project (Discovery Service)

- 1st TRIPLE ThatCamp: "Discovering Discovery" on May 11th
- Live! TRIPLE Crowdfunding Survey
- More TRIPLE News in a nutshell

Diamond OA Survey on Open Access Diamond Journals

Fragment from the April 2021 newsletter

As the metrics show, it was possible to double the number of subscribers during the time of the project. At the end of the project OPERAS had 268 subscribers for the newsletter.

4) Dissemination

In its definition by the EU, “dissemination means sharing research results with potential users - peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players and policymakers). By sharing your research results with the rest of the scientific community, you are contributing to the progress of science in general.”¹

There's often some overlap between dissemination, exploitation and communication. Therefore, it is not possible to divide the dissemination strictly from the communication. In this section we focus mainly on the spreading of the project results. Most other aspects were already mentioned above. The project results should be published open access.

The public project deliverables were published as drafts on Zenodo. All project deliverables were assigned a DOI, included the ORCID ID of the authors, and were uploaded to the Zenodo repository with links on the OPERAS website. All OPERAS-P deliverables (<https://www.operas-eu.org/projects/operas-p/>) and all OPERAS publications were featured on the website “bookshelf” (<https://www.operas-eu.org/about/bookshelf/>), where other key project related publications could also be found and were introduced with a short summary.

List of OPERAS-P Deliverables:

- D1.1 Collaborative web platform (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3635284](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3635284))
- D1.2 Data Management Plan (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3635300](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3635300))
- D3.1 Handbook for National Nodes (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4817771](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4817771))
- D3.4 Living Book (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4817743](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4817743))
- D4.1 Common access point to publication services specifications (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4817727](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4817727))
- D4.2 AAI service specifications (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4817710](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4817710))
- D4.4 A service to involve the communities: the Forum platform (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4817500](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4817500))
- D4.5 Protocol for the integration of OPERAS RI services into EOSC (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4005678](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4005678))
- D5.1 Requirements and specifications (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4817480](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4817480))
- D5.2 DOAB as a service (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4809241](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4809241))
- D6.1 Report on innovative models of governance (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4808411](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4808411))
- D6.2 Report on innovative business models in publishing (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4808411](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4808411))
- D6.3 Report on innovative approach to FAIR data (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4817525](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4817525))
- D6.4 Report on innovative models of bibliodiversity in scholarly publications (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4817509](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4817509))
- D6.5 Report on the future of scholarly writing in SSH (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4922512](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4922512))
- D6.6 Report on quality assessment of innovative research in SSH (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4922538](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4922538))

¹ European Commission: Dissemination & Exploitation of results, https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/dissemination-of-results_en.htm (25.06.2021)

- Future of Scholarly Communication . Forging an inclusive and innovative research infrastructure for scholarly communication in Social Sciences and Humanities (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.5017705](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5017705))
- D7.1 Communication and Dissemination Guide (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3635306](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3635306))
- D7.2 OPERAS-P Portal created (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3635312](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3635312))
- D7.3 Advocacy Guide (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4185703](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4185703))
- D7.4 Report of activities on communication, outreach and networking (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.5040520](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5040520))

a) Publications

- Balula, Ana, Leão, Delfim. “Multilingualism within Scholarly Communication in SSH – a literature review.” *JLIS.it* 12, 2 (May 2021): 00–00. DOI: [10.4403/jlis.it-12672](https://doi.org/10.4403/jlis.it-12672).
- Bertino, Andrea & Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra (2020). CO-OPERAS-SSHOC – Research data in the SSH [workshop report]. Presented in Goettingen Germany, 30 January 2020. *Zenodo*. (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3999331>)
- Blotière, Emilie, Suzanne Dumouchel, Laure Barbot, Gert Breiffuss, Yin Chen, Di Donato, Francesca, Paula Forbes, Clara Petitfils & Stefanie Pohle (2020). The TRIPLE project: Building a discovery platform to enhance collaboration (version final). *Zenodo*. (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3925735>)
- Borges, Maria Manuel (2020). CO-OPERAS – SSH FAIR data [workshop report]. Presented in Coimbra, Portugal on 6 December 2020. *Zenodo*. (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3999358>)
- Claire Clivaz and Garrick Allen (eds.) (2021, forthcoming). *Classics@ 18: Special issue on Virtual Research Environments and Ancient Manuscripts*. <https://chs.harvard.edu/classics18-ancient-manuscripts-and-virtual-research-environments/>
- Dumouchel, Suzanne, Francesca Di Donato, Monica Monachini, Yoann Moranville, Stefanie Pohle & Maria Eskevich (2020). Social sciences and humanities pathway towards the European open science cloud (version final). *Zenodo*. (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3898443>)
- Ernst, Elisabeth, Marlen Töpfer, Niels Cadée, Danielle Carter, Aysa Ekanger, Igor Goncharenko, Samir Hachani, Robert Isaksen, Judith Körte, Margreet Nieborg, Judith Schossboeck & Joke Verwaard (2020). How to fill the Information Gap: Open access for the social sciences and humanities (workshop report). Presented in Munin, France on 17 November 2020. *Zenodo*. (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4293341>)
- Ferwerda, Eelco (2020). Best practices in open access publishing. *Zenodo*. (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3624996>)
- Giglia, Elena (2020). CO-OPERAS- SSH FAIR data (workshop report). Presented in Brussels, Belgium on 3 March 2019. *Zenodo*. (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3999360>)
- Giglia, Elena, Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra & Peter Kraker (2020). CO-OPERAS – FAIR SSH (workshop report). Presented in Porto, Portugal 17 September 2019. *Zenodo*. (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3999345>)

- Giglia, Elena & Timea Biro (2020). Humanities and data: Towards a community driven path towards openness. *Zenodo*. (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3755505>)
- Elena Giglia (2020). Humanities and data: Listening to the communities on the path towards FAIRness. Presented at the Open Science Conference 2020 in Berlin, Germany on 11–12 March 2020. *Zenodo*. (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3776849>)
- Peter Kraker & Judith Schulte (2020). TRIPLE: A European discovery platform for the SSH. Presented at the Open Science Conference 2020 in Berlin, Germany on 11-12 March 2020. *Zenodo*. (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3776761>)
- Maryl, Maciej, Marta Błaszczczyńska, Agnieszka Szulińska & Paweł Rams (2020). The case for an inclusive scholarly communication infrastructure for social sciences and humanities. *F1000Research* 2020, 9: 1265. (<https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.26545.1>).
- Moranville, Yoann (2020). OPERAS Services – metrics service, certification service, publication service portal, discovery service. *Zenodo*. (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4266182>)
- Nury, Elisa and Claire Clivaz, with Marta Błaszczczyńska, Michael Kaiser, Agata Morka, Valérie Schaefer, Jadranka Stojanovski and Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra, “Open Research Data and Innovative Scholarly Writing: OPERAS highlights”, Proceedings of the Swiss Data Research Day 2020, Makhlouf Shabou Basma et al. (eds.), forthcoming.
- Nury, Elisa and Claire Clivaz with Marta Błaszczczyńska, Michael Kaiser, Agata Morka, Valérie Schaefer, Jadranka Stojanovski, Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra, and in collaboration with Vera Chiquet : “Research Data as a New Model of Scholarly Writing in SSH”; slides and video : <https://doi.org/10.34847/nkl.f734kiqd>
- Schulte, Judith (2020). Discovery-service TRIPLE. Presented at the DHd 2020 Spielräume: Digital Humanities zwischen Modellierung und Interpretation. 7. Tagung des Verbands "Digital Humanities im deutschsprachigen Raum" in Paderborn, Germany on 2–6 March 2020. *Zenodo*. (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4621910>)
- Tóth-Czifra, Erzsébet (2020). Rethinking text, techné and tenure: VREs as an evaluation and peer-review challenge in humanities. Presented at the SIB – SNSF MARK16 VREs conference in Lausanne, Switzerland on 10-11 September 2020. [Figshare:10.6084/m9.figshare.13557236.v1](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.13557236.v1)
- FAIR data in SSH: Needs and practices (2020). CO-OPERASCO-OPERAS French workshop report. Presented in Paris, France. 3 February 2020. *Zenodo*. (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3999352>)

Additionally to these publications on scientific magazines or Zenodo, the OPERAS website shall be a place to find and discuss research results as well.

In 2018, OPERAS consortium launched OPERAS White Papers as a vision statement advocating for Open Access in the SSH. Those documents constitute the practical and theoretical pillars on which OPERAS-P will stand to further enhance the development of the infrastructure.

- Since the publication date all documents have been viewed altogether almost 8,500 times and downloaded over 4,500 times, which indicates their relevance for the community. And although these papers provide a comprehensive, reliable overview of the state of the art, the AS French workshop report. Presented in Paris, France. 3 February 2020. *Zenodo*. (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3999352>) three years that

have passed since the day of their publication is a lot of time in scholarly communication.

This is why OPERAS decided to present revised and updated versions of the White Papers in the form of a living book.

[OPERAS Living Book](#) was published at the end of February 2021. The new versions of the OPERAS White Papers will be published in autumn 2021. We will apply open peer reviews to the Living Book using the [pund.it](#) plugin, developed by Net7. This will allow all pund.it registered users to add their comments to both individual fragments of text and entire white papers. In connection with this, we plan to conduct a “reviewathon”, approximately 2 week period during which reviewers (and authors) would be invited to comment on the papers. Special Interest Groups will be responsible for disseminating information about the reviewathon and for inviting reviewers to participate. The reviewathon will be organised and coordinated by Drahomira Cupar (Zadar University).

b) Videos

During the project, five videos were produced from OPERAS-P partners with the aim to introduce OPERAS and the OPERAS-P specific outputs. All were spread on the website and on the OPERAS social media channels.

The first video was produced in the beginning of the project with Elena Giglia presenting “Open Access Infrastructure in the Humanities and Social Sciences” as part of the Open Science Mooc. The video provided the opportunity to disseminate the idea of open science to a broader community through the Open Science Mooc:

<https://youtu.be/rlt-Y7zR-8Y>

<https://www.operas-eu.org/voices-from-the-community/>

The second one was produced by the University of Coimbra in regard to the first OPERAS General Assembly about the OPERAS vision and mission and the correlation to the University of Coimbra. It was produced in English but with Portuguese subtitles. This video was published on June 7, 2021 and pushed several weeks on the communication channels of Coimbra.

<https://youtu.be/xf0VAJfPNpk>

The three additional videos were produced with the support of the National Documentation Centre (EKT) highlighting some of the project key outputs. In particular, the videos produced presented: the OPERAS Forum “European Community in SSH”, the Publishing service portal “Pathfinder”, and the OPERAS Innovation Lab. They were published during the final OPERAS-P meeting on the social media channels. A decision was taken to keep the video duration short and the narrative simple. As a result the duration of each video is not more than 3 minutes.

The creation of the videos allowed OPERAS to reach the SSH community through a different channel and to communicate important OPERAS RI services to a wider audience (in addition to the use of social media and the organisation and participation in events). While the videos were launched towards the end of the project, we expect this communication channel to be

equally effective in disseminating the project results, given that all three of them will be operational even after the end of the project as part of the OPERAS RI. Their reception from the community could also help OPERAS in assessing the extent to which further videos should be produced.

OPERAS Forum: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NdrQNDEpBKA>

OPERAS Lab: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Elmv7_gxqbM

OPERAS Pathfinder: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oPD4UwS2qqQ&t=71s>

5) Main Impact, Increase of communication activities

The communication of the OPERAS RI during the OPERAS-P project was successful. During the duration of the OPERAS-P project, OPERAS was able to increase the audiences of the main communication channels (blog, website, twitter, newsletter) to a high extent. The number of newsletter followers could be doubled as well as the number of Twitter followers. The number of visits to the blog have been increasing by more than 60% during the OPERAS-P project. These are signs of raising awareness of the infrastructure. Thanks to a very active community and members, OPERAS was represented in lots of international conferences and was able to address different communities and target groups (SSH researchers, librarians, infrastructure providers, European Infrastructures, within the EOSC). Thanks to the activities of the national nodes it was possible to learn a lot about user's needs and challenges within the SSH scholarly communication all over Europe. As the metrics analysis has shown, that especially bigger conferences and surveys raised the attention on the blog and the social media channels. Both are instruments to get in contact and exchange with the community.

6) General Considerations

a) Open Science and dissemination

Open Science is defined as: Transparency in experimental methodology, observation, and collection of data.

- Public availability and reusability of research data.
- Public accessibility and transparency of scientific communication.
- Using open digital tools to facilitate scientific collaboration within research and between research and society.²

Regarding its understanding of Open Science, OPERAS has published not only its research results Open Access but communicated on the ongoing work during the project. The consortium decided to publish a high number of deliverables Open Access. They are all within the OPERAS Zenodo community and as one result of the OPERAS-P project, a new community OPERASLab was established for the innovative approaches of WP6.

² Dan Gezelter (2009-07-28), "What, Exactly, Is Open Science? | The OpenScience Project", accessed 30 December 2019, <http://openscience.org/what-exactly-is-open-science/>. – OECD (2015-10-15), "Making Open Science a Reality", OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers, No. 25, OECD Publishing, Paris, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/5jrs2f963zs1-en>.

b) How the pandemic affected the work in the WP

WP7 is largely devoted to outreach and networking activities. As the pandemic started in early 2020, we were unable to meet in person. Networking and outreach are the activities affected the most by the crisis, as they are almost impossible to be carried out in a virtual environment. Online meetings can substitute ordinary project meetings and can replicate workshops and conferences to some extent – at least to share contents and ideas –, but they can't recreate those unique informal moments in which people can connect, interact, and trigger new connections. The results of outreach and networking outputs will hence be more limited than expected and consumed more capacity, as events had to be rescheduled and extensively restructured to function online, as for example the OPERAS2020 conference, which was planned as a face-to-face conference in Brussels together with the Royal Library of Belgium and was first moved to November 2020 and then restructured to an online event.

c) Future plans and considerations

The work that has been done shall be continued within the next few years. The dissemination of the results has only just started and shall be continued the next month and years. The OPERAS RI will take care of the website, the blog and the channels. The newsletter will be continued as well. The strategy for the LinkedIn account needs to be adapted. To highlight the results of WP6 it is planned to have a page on the website for the OPERASLab as the place of OPERAS innovations.

During the project and the establishing of national nodes, the importance of active members in different countries as the best possibility to reach out to national communities became obvious and their role shall be improved in the future. As the OPERAS RI is a growing infrastructure the role of the communication will be even more important in the future.

7) Outreach for new members (Task 7.2)

The goal of this Task was to identify potential OPERAS members, i.e. organizations that fulfill the requirements and are interested in becoming members of the OPERAS RI, and to define a strategy for reaching out to new members. The task was led by the National Documentation Centre (EKT).

a) Definition of Outreach

According to the Cambridge Dictionary, outreach is the “effort to bring services or information to people where they live or spend time”, or according to the Merriam-Webster dictionary “is the act of reaching out”, or “an effort to build connections from one person or group to another” (GCIDE). The above are only some of the definitions for outreach, the most relevant to what is meant by outreach in the context of the OPERAS-P project and the Task 7.2 more precisely, which is to identify and integrate relevant European stakeholders into the OPERAS infrastructure.

b) Activities and Results

The outreach for new members is an approach of many stages.

The first step of this procedure was to identify the institutions eligible to become OPERAS members, in order to identify the primary targets of the outreach task. For this purpose the *Landscape Study on scholarly needs and stakeholders in social sciences and humanities* that was produced in the context of the WP2 of the OPERAS-P, has been exploited. The purpose of this study was to investigate the open scholarly communication landscape in SSH on the national level for all core countries of the OPERAS RI and to identify relevant stakeholders.

Based on this study a list of potential members for each one of the core member countries was created. 10 lists, one for each country (Croatia, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia, UK) have been prepared. 5 types of stakeholders were identified as the most relevant to start with for outreaching to new members. These are: University Presses, Library Based Publishers, Scholar-led Publishers, Repositories and Platforms, Commercial Publishers. The number of organisations per category follows: University Presses (51), Library Based Publishers (31), Scholar-led Publishers (9), Repositories and Platforms (39), Commercial Publishers (7). Contacting all these organizations simultaneously was not feasible nor desirable so a prioritization of the actions and contacts had to be made. This was made possible with the cooperation of the Executive Assembly members.

For the purpose of new member outreach, a dedicated session titled “How to join OPERAS” was organised in the context of the OPERAS Conference “Opening up Social Sciences and Humanities in Europe: From Promises to Reality” that took place from the 2nd to the 4th of November 2020. This session gathered (virtually) organisations interested in joining OPERAS RI. The participants had the opportunity to listen to OPERAS core members, and

discuss with them about their potential role in the OPERAS RI and what it means to work collaboratively within the OPERAS RI network. In this meeting the different types of OPERAS membership were presented, as well as the OPERAS Special Interest Groups (SIGs), as SIGs serve as an entry door for new OPERAS members. This session had 50 attendants (approx.) representing 11 organisations that are not OPERAS members. As a follow up to the “How to join OPERAS ” session, organisations that attended were contacted via email in order to investigate their intentions and inform them about the benefits of becoming OPERAS members.

By exploiting the lists that were created from the Landscape Study and the “How to Join OPERAS” session, six organisations were contacted. One organisation has shown interest in becoming an OPERAS member but the rest of them have not responded. The first contact in all of these cases was made via email due to the situation that has been shaped by the pandemic and the consequent social distancing. As this is an impersonal type of communication that does not allow the building of trust and familiarity among people, the results were not very successful since most of the people that were contacted did not respond.

For the most effective communication about what it means to be an OPERAS member, including the benefits and obligations that arise from the OPERAS membership, informational material was produced for a brief and to-the-point presentation of these issues. In the document (that can be found here

https://www.operas-eu.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/OPERAS_Outreach_Text_Final.pdf)

one can find the types of OPERAS membership, the reasons to become an OPERAS member, and what it means to work collaboratively in OPERAS through the participation in the OPERAS SIGs. An extract of this document follows:

Why to join OPERAS?

The European landscape of scholarly communication in the SSH is currently patchy, and not organized enough to be efficient, particularly to address the challenge of transitioning to Open Science. OPERAS' keyword is coordination against the SSH fragmentation in sub disciplines, national languages, specific communication channels tailored to specific research objects or to specific communities. Participation in OPERAS is crucial for the transition to Open Science and all the participants can enjoy the benefits of this transition.

OPERAS nurtures the players, even smaller one, pooling and combining services at scale. By gathering a consortium encompassing a large number of players in the European Research Area (ERA), OPERAS will allow partners to benefit from each other and share their research and development costs. Hence it will leverage existing innovation in Europe to bring the whole ecosystem together at the highest level.

Participation in OPERAS will help the national nodes to attract funding from the European Commission, but also from national and regional authorities, to support and expand their activities.

What does it mean to be an OPERAS Member?

There are three different kinds of memberships, which correspond to three different levels of engagement in the life and activities of OPERAS. An institution may choose the type of membership that is most suitable to its role in the scholarly communication landscape and its particular needs. These types are the following:

- **Ordinary member:** to participate in at least one Special Interest Group equivalent to 10% Full-time Equivalent (FTE) commitment in-kind, with voting rights in the Assembly of the Commons.
- **Core member:** to participate in the Assembly of the Commons and the Executive Assembly, equivalent to 20% FTE commitment in-kind, with voting rights in the Assembly of the Commons and the Executive Assembly.
- **Supporting member:** to shape OPERAS' strategy and future activities in participating and voting in the General Assembly. To support OPERAS AISBL by an annual membership fee and a close relationship - with privileged access to the life and activities of the association.

The participation in OPERAS presupposes the commitment a) to support the development of open science and open access, particularly in the social sciences and the humanities, and b) to follow the principles for open scholarly infrastructures and the FAIR Principles. For this purpose a document explaining the rules of participation in OPERAS was produced in order

to present and explain the rules and procedures that members must follow in the context of OPERAS. The text can be found here:

https://operas.hypotheses.org/files/2020/02/OPERAS_Rules_of_Participation.pdf

Rules of
Participation

January 2020

Both documents can be found on the following page:

<https://www.operas-eu.org/about/want-to-know-more/want-to-join-operas/>

The core group members of OPERAS have organised national events in their efforts to engage the communities of their own countries and build National Nodes for OPERAS. The German event took place on the 27th of April, the Italian event on the 13th of May, the Greek event on the 26th of May, the Polish event on the 17th of June and the Dutch one on the 22nd of the same month. The purpose of these events was to organise the communities of these countries on the basis of best practices, but they also have the role to communicate OPERAS RI to local communities and outreach for new members in the audiences of their own countries. There were national events, in Greece for example, in which organisations from outside the country, and more particularly from Cyprus, attended, which gave the opportunity to outreach for new members outside the core member countries as well.

During the OPERAS-P project the following organisations joined OPERAS as ordinary member: Associação Portuguesa de Editoras do Ensino Superior, Digital Humanities (Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics), the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences of Zagreb University, the Centre for Evaluation in Education and Science of Serbia, Academy of Fine Arts Vienna, Firenze University Press, SPARC Europe and the National Library of Sweden. There are also three new supporting members: DGLFLF – La délégation générale à la langue française et aux langues de France, Göttingen SUB, the State and University Library and DARIAH ERIC.

c) Future Strategy

OPERAS RI is continuously evolving and expanding, so the outreach for new members is a task that does not end with the OPERAS-P project. The lists of potential members and organisations that are interested in joining OPERAS is an important tool that can be used to outreach for new members. In this effort the National Nodes that have been or will be created in the core countries will have a crucial role to play. Now that the audiences of OPERAS in the core countries are well defined and well known, they can be targeted for future outreach activities. National Nodes will facilitate the creation of coherent communities, and as a result OPERAS will reach its audience in a more effective way. Outreach tasks that can be used in the future are one to one contacts with organisations that have been identified as potential members, the organisation of trainings and webinars in order to familiarise local communities with Open Science in general and OPERAS in particular, as well as the the organisation of workshops and conferences where local communities can discuss their needs and the challenges they face and how OPERAS RI is related to them.

d) Conclusion

The outreach for new members is a task that has been affected by the constraints imposed by the pandemic. Nevertheless, new members have joined OPERAS and the strategy for attracting new members has been defined, as the target audiences are well recognised and the strategy to contact them through National Nodes is well established.

8) Networking (Task 7.3)

As part of Task 7.3, networking strategies were developed and implemented. This task was led by the University of Torino.

a. Definition of Networking

“Networking” has so many different meanings according to the environment it refers to. The most relevant definition for WP7 is the Business Network one, “A business network is a type of business social network which is developed to help business people connect with other managers and entrepreneurs to further each other's business interests by forming mutually beneficial business relationships. Business networking is a way of leveraging your business and personal connections to help you bring in new customers, vendors or just get great advice for running your business” [Wikipedia]. What is interesting here is the idea of something expanding, which is in the nature of a “net”, and the idea of mutually beneficial relationships, which as OPERAS we translated into the idea of “strategic alliances”. The term “connection” is also crucial, as the Cambridge Dictionary definition highlights: “a large system consisting of many similar parts that are connected together”. The Merriam-Webster dictionary underlines another crucial aspect of “networking”, which is the exchange of information: “the exchange of information or services among individuals, groups, or institutions”.

The definition which best suits the OPERAS' idea of “networking” actually is “the exchange of information and ideas among people with a common profession or special interest, usually in an informal social setting. Networking often begins with a single point of common ground” ([Investopedia](#)). The term to focus on here is “informal”, as networking typically happens at conferences, during informal breaks or Q&A sessions.

These informal moments were the ones most affected by the sanitary crisis created by the pandemic, as activities in person were dramatically reduced. Hence, the further expansion of the network was limited and results were mainly achieved by leveraging on the existing network created before the pandemic.

b. Activities and results

The above mentioned definitions of “networking” are aligned with the objectives of Task 7.3, which was threefold:

1. to create strong strategic alliances outside the OPERAS consortium,
2. to position OPERAS as a recognized player in the Open Science political arena
3. to gather around OPERAS, a lively community, starting with early career researchers.

OPERAS managed to achieve important and strategic tasks, notwithstanding the pandemic situation, on all these 3 axes. As a result, OPERAS now holds a stronger place in the SSH field in Europe, and has developed stronger alliances with the the key players, as detailed below:

1. Alliances

OPERAS strengthened the alliance with DARIAH Eric and SPARC Europe.

With DARIAH, OPERAS has a longstanding tradition of jointly organising workshops and conferences. Together, they curate the Open Methods hub (<https://openmethods.dariah.eu/>) to highlight digital humanities tools and methods (information on other collaborations <https://operas.hypotheses.org/2863>). DARIAH joined OPERAS as a supporting member.

Along with SPARC Europe and other players (DOAB - Directory of Open Access Books; OAPEN Foundation; the COPIM project) OPERAS founded the Open Access Books Network on Humanities Commons, (<https://openaccessbooksnetwork.hcommons.org/>) a “space for passionate conversations about OA books. Researchers, publishers, librarians, infrastructure providers — indeed, anyone who is interested — can discuss any aspect of OA books”. SPARC Europe and OPERAS are both involved in the Steering committee of the Invest in Open Infrastructure Initiative (<https://investinopen.org/>).

OPERAS led the Diamond consortium in order to fulfill the CoalitionS’ appointment on the survey on Diamond Open Access journals (<https://operas.hypotheses.org/4141>), which is one of the topics gaining more views on the blog and more downloads on Zenodo. For the Diamond consortium, strategic alliances with important organisations such as SPARC Europe, Readlyc/Ameli.ca, LIBER, OASPA were put in place or reinforced. Particularly meaningful is the alliance with OASPA, as many visitors to the OPERAS website have been conveyed via the OASPA website.

OPERAS also created new synergies with the Go FAIR initiative, setting the CO-OPERAS Implementation Network devoted to the FAIRification of data in the Humanities (<https://www.go-fair.org/implementation-networks/overview/co-operas/>); Suzanne Dumouchel has been elected to the Go FAIR Executive Board and Elena Giglia to the Go FAIR Stakeholder Forum. Activities like workshops [see the Reports in Zenodo, and also WP6.3 report] and focus groups have been carried out jointly. A collaboration on a Train the Trainers programme on data in the Humanities with the Brazilian chapter of Go FAIR started in early 2020, but was interrupted by the pandemic.

OPERAS is also represented by Suzanne Dumouchel in the SSHOC cluster project for the Humanities in the EOSC. In 2021, OPERAS also collaborated with the regional EOSC project EOSC Pillar and the Competence Center of the Italian consortium ICDI to design and deliver a 20 hour course on Open Science and FAIR data management in the Social Sciences and the Humanities. The course is composed of 10 hours of theory and 10 hours of practice, involving and presenting the services and the activities of Research Infrastructures. The course was held in May/June 2021 at the Italian National Research Council (CNR) institutes in the Humanities and Cultural Heritage domain. It is planned to be delivered to other institutions and participating countries in the EOSC Pillar project.

2. OPERAS in the arena

CoalitionS commissioned OPERAS to conduct a large scale study on Open Access journals across the world that are free for readers and authors, usually referred to as “OA diamond journals”. The results are available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4558703>). This can be seen as a first step in the collaboration among OPERAS and CoalitionS. Further common initiatives are expected on the inclusion of books into PlanS. Both are a recognition of the role OPERAS is playing in the community.

OPERAS joined the EOSC Association in December 2020, and is now a member. Suzanne Dumouchel was voted onto the Board of Directors and Elena Giglia is OPERAS representative in the General Assembly (see more <https://operas.hypotheses.org/4544>).

3. Creating a community, starting with Early Career Researchers

EURODOC provided a Letter of Support for the OPERAS ESFRI Application in 2020, and there were fruitful meetings and discussions among the coordinators of the two associations. The University of Turin, task Leader of the WP7.3 of OPERAS-P, also started a fruitful collaboration with four European universities within the Horizon2020 SWAFS project “ISPAS-Paths to successful innovation” (University of Stavanger, University of Girona, IMIBAS - Bulgaria, IDIBELL). Another partner involved in the ISPAS project is Fondazione1563, a foundation linked to Compagnia di San Paolo, which is one of the main private research funders in Italy. Fondazione1563 is interested in joining OPERAS, and it is actively collaborating with the University of Turin on ISPAS training courses. ISPAS is targeting Early Career Researchers with an approach linking Open Science to Open Innovation. The 20 hours course on Open Science and FAIR data basics can be a powerful leverage to gather a community, even though ISPAS is discipline-neutral.

OPERAS National Nodes play a crucial role in creating a community. Some started to build national communities by holding national workshops as part of WP3.3 (see the workshop reports in this paper).

The Advocacy workshops targeting specific communities (see below, chapter on Advocacy) can also be an international, transversal leverage to network with different players.

c. Further initiatives

Being a member of the EOSC Association, OPERAS will be involved in the EOSC Advisory Groups, which will be an important way to network with people and projects. Within the EOSC framework, a stricter networking and synergy creation should be foreseen with the SSHOC cluster project and regional projects such as EOSC Pillar. Here, the CO-OPERAS network can play a role in bundling together the SSH-related research infrastructures and cluster projects to effectively tackle the FAIR principles adoption.

The collaboration with CoalitionS can result in more networking opportunities, as well as the ongoing joint work with SPARC Europe and DARIAH ERIC.

The ongoing collaboration with EGI has been reinforced during the ESFRI application phase, as well as the TRIPLE project (gotriple.eu); OPERAS is also taking part in the EGI ACE project as the SSH community.

OPERAS is also collaborating more actively with OpenAIRE, e.g. being asked to be part of the Organizing committee of the Open Science Fair in September 2021 (<https://twitter.com/OpenScienceFAIR/status/1403275821947707393>).

Working together with these major players in the Open Science arena, OPERAS paved the way for a more interconnected and hence effective ecosystem within the EOSC framework.

9) Advocacy towards researchers (Task 7.4)

Within this task an advocacy strategy towards researchers was developed and advocacy workshops held to reach out to different stakeholder groups. This task was led by Max Weber Stiftung. A first version of an Advocacy Guide was produced in October 2020 and an updated and extended version in June 2021 (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4185702>).

a) Definition of Advocacy

Communication activities usually encompass all activities that focus on an exchange of information. Advocacy and lobbying actions are a part of communication activities with a more specific goal.

The term “advocacy” is often used to describe an activity or process of “supporting a cause or proposal” (see Merriam Webster dictionary) and especially gaining “public support” (see Cambridge Dictionary) for this activity or idea. The activity can be carried out either by an individual or group. Organizations describing their advocacy activities most commonly use the term to show how they create central positions and use them to influence positions of political, public or economic institutions, e.g. the bodies of the European Union. This process often takes place by including a broader public community, both from within the organizations and from without. The advocacy process often works in both directions: organizations include public opinion in their creation of central positions but, at the same time, strive to influence public opinion.

The definitions of “lobbying” are much clearer than those for “advocacy”. The term is usually used to describe “activities aimed at influencing public officials and especially members of a legislative body on legislation” (see Merriam Webster dictionary). It is thus a form of advocacy that concentrates on approaching legislators directly.³

Fig. 1: The scope of communication, advocacy, and lobbying. Created by Elisabeth Ernst and Marlen Töpfer. CC BY 4.0.

³ Advocacy definition DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4185702>

b) Advocacy Workshops and results

As part of Task 7.4 three workshops were held to address different stakeholder groups (publishers and publishing platforms, libraries and infrastructure providers, universities and research organizations) to help them by addressing researchers' concerns in SSH and to better understand how the other stakeholder groups can advocate for OA publishing with researchers. Due to the pandemic situation all workshops have been held virtually.

1. for libraries

Title: “OPERAS advocacy workshop Libraries supporting Open Science” (University of Turin)

Date: June 8, 2021

N of attendants: 33

Stakeholders: librarians, open access staff

Topics: supporting services to enable Open Science, synergies creation, community engagement, institutional roadmaps to Open Science and concrete implementation..

Documentation/Reports: Video recording and slides of the event:

<https://www.oa.unito.it/new/operas-advocacy-workshop-june-8-2021/>

Summary:

Presented three successful experiences of libraries offering services and support to enable Open Science practices among researchers. The speakers gave complementary and insightful perspectives on the different levels in which a library can support the 8 pillars of Open Science, always focusing on listening to the users' needs and providing services.

Supporting the future of scholarly communication in the form of a successful University Press like UCL press is a good practice to be followed. The platform offers innovative services and perfectly matches the needs of researchers, as the success in terms of both publications and downloads testify.

The message coming from TU Delft is as well important: engage the community to speak the same language, as sometimes “Open Science” can be seen as an abstract term until experts and the community meet: the result is that researchers acknowledged they were already doing Open Science, without calling it that name. Another highlight is the creation of a single-stop point to access Open Science related services, pooling different expertises (data management, legal advice, library advice on Open Access, IT support...) to ease the life of researchers and make Open Science easy.

The good practice of the University of Barcelona is in the setting of an institutional roadmap and in its concrete implementation, with the creation of a specific Open Science unit pooling again different expertises and being part of the policy making process.

Paul Ayris, University College London, [Open Science, a blueprint for Universities in the 21st century?](#)

Emmy Tsang, TU Delft, [Towards a community-centric approach to designing institutional support for Open Science](#)

Ignasi Labastida, University of Barcelona, [Supporting Open Science practices and policies from the library](#)

2. for publishers

Title: “Publishers and Publishing Stances: a Contribution to Multilingualism and Scholarly Communication” (Workshop from SIGs on Advocacy and Multilingualism) (University of Coimbra)

Date: April 22nd, 2021

N of attendants: 120 registered, approx. 60 during the whole event.

Stakeholders: Publishers, Researchers on the SSH, PhD students, librarians

Topics: Results and recommendations from the OA diamond journals study, multilingualism in Ibero-American academic publishers, contributions to multilingualism, bibliodiversity, Open Access.

Documentation/Reports: operas-eu.org/4690

Summary - The workshop “Publishers and Publishing Stances - A Contribution to Multilingualism and Bibliodiversity” was organised in two panels. The first one was dedicated to present the results, findings and recommendations from the first multi-institutional study on the Open Access Diamond Journals, with a special focus on the Latin-American context. The first panel was moderated by Delfim Leão, Vice-Rector for Culture and Open Science at the University of Coimbra and the speakers included Pierre Mounier, community coordinator of OPERAS and deputy director of OpenEdition, and Arianna Becerril-García, founder member of Redalyc (Network of Scientific Journals from Latin America and the Caribbean, Spain and Portugal) and professor at UAEM (México).

The second panel was specially dedicated to discuss the different perspectives of University Presses publishers and associations in the Ibero-American space. The panel was moderated by Margo Bargheer, from the Association of European Academic Presses – AEUP and Universität Göttingen. The speakers represented different areas from the Iberoamerican landscape of academic publishers: from Portugal, João Caetano (APEES – Associação Portuguesa de Editoras do Ensino Superior and Universidade Aberta); from Spain, Ana Isabel González (Unión de Editoriales Universitarias Españolas – UNE and Universidad de Oviedo); from Brazil, Jézio Hernani Gutierre (Associação Brasileira de Editoras Universitárias – ABEU and Universidade Estadual Paulista Júlio de Mesquita Filho – Unesp); and representing the region of Latin America and Caribbean, Sayri Karp Mitastein (Asociación de Editoriales Universitarias de América Latina y el Caribe – EULAC and Universidad de Guadalajara).

Link to the full report and video recording of the workshop:

<https://operas.hypotheses.org/4690>

3. for universities

Title: “How to fill the information gap: Open Access for the social sciences and humanities”, Advocacy Workshop for researchers (MWS)

Date: November 17, 2020

N of attendants: 12

Stakeholders: Researchers on the SSH, PhD students, librarians/open access staff

Topics: Open Access publishing possibilities and challenges in social sciences and humanities

Documentation/Reports: Full report: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4293340>; Blog post: [//operas-eu.org/4435](https://operas-eu.org/4435)

Summary and results:

The OPERAS workshop “How to fill the information gap: Open Access for the social sciences and humanities” took place on 17 November 2020 as part of the 15th Munin Conference on Scholarly Publishing 2020. Participants were asked to fill in a survey prior to the workshop. The results can be found in the report (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4293340>)

The discussion showed that overviews over Open Access publishing possibilities, especially for journals, have been strongly evolved and are already of good quality in many countries. Yet, this is not true for all European countries and particularly so for Open Access publishing of monographs and books. The problem that researchers are afraid of losing reputation seems to not be a prevailing issue and, indeed, in some disciplines and for journal articles not the case anymore. The situation for books has not been discussed during the workshop. Many participants criticized that repository publishing options are often not much advised and that green Open Access is not part of the debate.

During the discussion it became clear that the community-debate should not be—and often already is not—focusing on transforming Open Access anymore. Rather, it should be about building the “house” for Open Access.

The “Why’s” are dead – long life the “How’s”!

Future Plans:

The Advocacy Special Interest Group included the results in their update of the Advocacy Guide to give guidelines for Advocacy in SSH and researchers needs regarding OA publishing. They will continue the advocacy work after the end of OPERAS-P. Yet, many of the results and recommendations can also be adapted for further use for advocacy actions in different contexts and can help the national nodes within their national communities. The role of the national nodes shall be strengthened in future projects.

Appendix:

Examples of communication activities of partners in detail:

Tweets on OPERAS-P results:

- March 4 and 29, 2020, Tweet related to OPERAS Governance Survey, inviting the community to answer it:
https://twitter.com/valerie_schafer/status/1235215801243906050
- https://twitter.com/valerie_schafer/status/1244365638069620738
- July 23, 2020: several tweets advertising the Knowledge infrastructure and Digital Governance Conference
https://twitter.com/valerie_schafer/status/1286224639665020928
- September 7 and 8, 2021 Live tweets during the Knowledge infrastructure and Digital Governance Conference (C2DH, UL)
https://twitter.com/DEIP_World/status/1302924194578083841
- October 16, 2020 tweet on the publication of the report of the Governance workshop:
https://twitter.com/valerie_schafer/status/1317053023001169920
- February 12, 2021, Tweet advertising the panel on Governance during the workshop “The future of Scholarly Communication”
https://twitter.com/valerie_schafer/status/1360341701181718532
- April 30, 2021: Dissemination TRIPLÉ crowdfunding questionnaire:
<https://twitter.com/ImprensaUC/status/1388154994441007111?s=20>
- April 26, 2021: Dissemination of first TRIPLÉ ThatCamp:
<https://twitter.com/ImprensaUC/status/1386636838232903684?s=20>
- April 19, 2021: Dissemination of the Advocacy and Multilingualism workshop - retweet from OPERAS -
<https://twitter.com/OPERASEU/status/1384099663398064135?s=20>
- April 16, 2021: Retweet for the dissemination of the Multilingualism workshop, focusing on the results of the OA diamond study:
<https://twitter.com/ImprensaUC/status/1383081073719058435?s=20>
- April 13, 2021: Dissemination of TRIPLÉ training on Open Research Europe:
<https://twitter.com/ImprensaUC/status/1381946179831877637?s=20>
- April 12, 2021: Reminder for registering at the Multilingualism and bibliodiversity workshop at Coimbra:
<https://twitter.com/ImprensaUC/status/1381645755157512193?s=20>
- April 9, 2021: Dissemination of the blog post from OPERAS about the workshop on multilingualism and bibliodiversity to be held in Coimbra:
<https://twitter.com/ImprensaUC/status/1380468804149522434?s=20>
- March 25, 2021: Dissemination of the last days for participation in the OA Books study from OPERAS-P.
<https://twitter.com/ImprensaUC/status/1375126852843495427?s=20>

- March 16, 2021: Dissemination of the survey by OPERAS on OA Books: <https://twitter.com/ImprensaUC/status/1372185961413623819?s=20>
- March 8, 2021: Dissemination of the report on open access books by OPERAS-P and COPIM. <https://twitter.com/ImprensaUC/status/1368947113640550402?s=20>
- February 22, 2021: Dissemination of the Future of Scholarly Communication workshop from OPERAS-P. <https://twitter.com/ImprensaUC/status/1363851043419774978?s=20>
- February 16, 2021: Retweet from Delfim Leão with the link from UC Open Science website news article on Future of Scholarly Communication workshop from OPERAS-P. <https://twitter.com/DelfimLeao/status/1361713244956741635?s=20>
- February 9, 2021: Dissemination of PKP and OPERAS community forum: <https://twitter.com/ImprensaUC/status/1359064497500131328?s=20>
- November 2, 2020: Retweet from OPERAS - Annual conference start. <https://twitter.com/OPERASEU/status/1323158026598158348?s=20>
- October 29, 2020: Dissemination for the OPERAS annual conference, with link for news article from UC Open Science and retweet from OPERAS. <https://twitter.com/ImprensaUC/status/1321819347359322117?s=20>
- October 23, 2020: Dissemination by OPERAS (retweet) celebrating the accomplishment of 600 books from Coimbra University Press on DOAB. <https://twitter.com/ImprensaUC/status/1319565527912714240?s=20>
- October 15, 2020: Dissemination of a panel for OPERAS annual conference - retweet from OPERAS. <https://twitter.com/OPERASEU/status/1316678518156095488?s=20>
- October 7, 2020: Retweet of OPERAS for the dissemination of open registrations to the annual conference. <https://twitter.com/OPERASEU/status/1313777577245446144?s=20>
- July 28, 2020: Dissemination of the survey from OPERAS and cOAlition S about diamond journals, with link for news article on UC Open Science website. <https://twitter.com/ImprensaUC/status/1288108940266414080?s=20>
- July 8, 2020: Dissemination of the open library initiative from OPERAS focused on references about Covid-19. <https://twitter.com/ImprensaUC/status/1280849114025070592?s=20>
- June 25, 2020: Dissemination of survey on multilingualism from OPERAS SIG. <https://twitter.com/ImprensaUC/status/1276062574950277120?s=20>
- June 22, 2020: Call for researchers, translators and publishers for answering the multilingualism survey. <https://twitter.com/ImprensaUC/status/1275005768593551361?s=20>
- June 18, 2020: Retweet of Pierre Mounier about the reception of the first 13 applications for the Scientific Advisory Committee of OPERAS. <https://twitter.com/piotrr70/status/1273611933611175940?s=20>
- June 15, 2020: Retweet of the OPERAS post calling for applications for the Scientific Advisory Committee. <https://twitter.com/OPERASEU/status/1272440216440184833?s=20>
- June 8, 2020: OPERAS selection for Scientific Advisory Committee dissemination: <https://twitter.com/ImprensaUC/status/1269977478849630208?s=20>
- April 8, 2020: OPERAS survey on SSH scholarly communication: <https://twitter.com/ImprensaUC/status/1247840643411587072?s=20>

- March 16, 2020: Call for researchers to answer the survey on SSH scholarly communication from OPERAS:
<https://twitter.com/ImprensaUC/status/1239481606575972353?s=20>
- March 13, 2020: OPERAS survey on scholarly communication -
<https://twitter.com/ImprensaUC/status/1238486047840972800?s=20>

Facebook

- April 9, 2021: Dissemination of the workshop on Multilingualism and Bibliodiversity for Publishers from SIGs on Multilingualism and Advocacy.
<https://www.facebook.com/ImprensaUC/posts/10159833042946282>
- March 25, 2021: Dissemination of the deadline extension for publishers to answering the OA Books survey by OPERAS-P.
<https://www.facebook.com/ImprensaUC/posts/10159791545051282>
- March 17, 2021: Dissemination of COESo survey on citizen science crowdfunding.
<https://www.facebook.com/ImprensaUC/posts/10159766394481282>
- March 8, 2021: Dissemination for the release of OA Books landscape study by OPERAS-P and COPIM.
<https://www.facebook.com/ImprensaUC/posts/10159741822261282>
- February 22, 2021: Dissemination of OPERAS-P Future of Scholarly Communication workshop. <https://www.facebook.com/ImprensaUC/posts/10159702283536282>
- February 9, 2021: Dissemination of the launch of OPERAS Forum at PKP community: <https://www.facebook.com/ImprensaUC/posts/10159662517616282>
- November 23, 2020: Dissemination of the participation of CO-OPERAS and TRIPLE projects workshops at the International FAIR Convergence Symposium.
<https://www.facebook.com/ImprensaUC/posts/10159409057471282>
- July 28, 2020: Dissemination of Diamond OA survey.
<https://www.facebook.com/ImprensaUC/posts/10159065139526282>
- June 22, 2020: Dissemination of the multilingualism survey from OPERAS-P:
<https://www.facebook.com/ImprensaUC/posts/10158941818256282>
- June 8, 2020: Dissemination of open submissions for OPERAS Scientific Advisory Committee. <https://www.facebook.com/ImprensaUC/posts/10158893258996282>
- April 8, 2020: Call for participation in the OPERAS SSH scholarly communication survey. <https://www.facebook.com/ImprensaUC/posts/10158641301671282>
- March 13, 2020: Dissemination of the survey on scholarly communication in the SSH by OPERAS. <https://www.facebook.com/ImprensaUC/posts/10158530887416282>